

Home.aspx

Client side coding:

```
<%@ Page Language="C#" AutoEventWireup="true" CodeFile="Home.aspx.cs"
Inherits="Index" %>
```

```
<!DOCTYPE html PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD XHTML 1.0 Transitional//EN"
"http://www.w3.org/TR/xhtml1/DTD/xhtml1-transitional.dtd">
```

```
<script runat="server">
```

```
    protected void btnSignIn_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {

    }
</script>
```

```
<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml" >
<head id="Head1" runat="server">
    <title>Welcome!</title>
    <!-- slideshow---***** 3d*****-->
    <script type="text/javascript" language="javascript">
        function Check()
        {
            if(document.getElementById("txtUserName").value == "")
            {
                alert("Please Enter Name");
                return false;
            }

            if(document.getElementById("txtPassword").value == "")
            {
                alert("Please Enter Password");
                return false;
            }

            return true;
        }
    </script>
```

```
<style type="text/css">
#carousel{

    width:900px;
    height:200px;
    position:relative;
    border:0px ;
}
/*img{
```

```

        width:100%;
        height:100%;
        border:0px ;
    }*/

</style>
<script src="menu/mootools.js" type="text/javascript"></script>

<script src="menu/3dcarousel.js" type="text/javascript"></script>

    <style type="text/css">

/*Credits: By Santosh Setty (http://webdesigninfo.wordpress.com) */
/*Posted to: Dynamic Drive CSS Library (http://www.dynamicdrive.com/style/)
*/

.glossymenu{
    position: relative;
    padding: 0 0 0 10px;
    margin: 0 auto 0 auto;
    background: url(menu/menub_bg.gif) repeat-x; /*tab background image
path*/
    height: 46px;
    list-style: none;
}

.glossymenu li{
    float:left;
}

.glossymenu li a{
    float: left;
    display: block;
    color:#000;
    text-decoration: none;
    font-family: sans-serif;
    font-size: 15px;
    font-weight: bold;
    padding:0 0 0 18px; /*Padding to accomodate left tab image. Do not
change*/
    height: 46px;
    line-height: 46px;
    text-align: center;
    cursor: pointer;
}

.glossymenu li a b{
    float: left;
    display: block;
    padding: 0 20px 0 20px; /*Padding of menu items*/
}

.glossymenu li.current a, .glossymenu li a:hover{
    color: #fff;
    background: url(menu/menub_hover_left.gif) no-repeat; /*left tab image
path*/
    background-position: left;

```

```

}

.glossymenu li.current a b, .glossymenu li a:hover b{
    color: #fff;
    background: url(menu/menub_hover_right.gif) no-repeat right top;
/*right tab image path*/
}

</style>
<script type="text/javascript" language="JavaScript1.1">
<!--

/*
JavaScript Image slideshow:
By (www.wsabstract.com)
Over 200+ free JavaScript here!
*/

var slideimages=new Array()
var slidelinks=new Array()
function slideshowimages(){
for (i=0;i<slideshowimages.arguments.length;i++){
slideimages[i]=new Image()
slideimages[i].src=slideshowimages.arguments[i]
}
}

function slideshowlinks(){
for (i=0;i<slideshowlinks.arguments.length;i++)
slidelinks[i]=slideshowlinks.arguments[i]
}

function gotoshow(){
if (!window.winslide||winslide.closed)
winslide=window.open(slidelinks[whichlink])
else
winslide.location=slidelinks[whichlink]
winslide.focus()
}

//-->
</script>
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=iso-8859-1"
/>

<meta name="description" content="2011 International Conference on Computing
and Computer Vision" />

<meta content="Ziad Kobti" name="Author" />

<meta http-equiv="Content-Style-Type" content="text/css" />
<meta content="MSHTML 6.00.6000.16735" name="GENERATOR" />

<meta http-equiv="content-type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
<meta http-equiv="imagetoolbar" content="no" />

```

```

    <meta name="keywords" content="slideman, sliderman.js, javascript
slider, jquery, slideshow, effects" />
    <meta name="description" content="Sliderman.js - will do all the
sliding for you :)" />
    <style type="text/css">
        * { margin: 0; outline: none; }
        body { background-color: #444444; }
        .c { clear: both; }
        #wrapper { margin: 0 auto; width: 560px; }
        h2 { font-size: 24px; line-height: 40px; font-weight: normal;
color: #adc276; text-shadow: 0 1px 3px #222222; }
    </style>
    <style type="text/css">

/*Credits: Dynamic Drive CSS Library */
/*URL: http://www.dynamicdrive.com/style/ */

.sidebarmenu ul{
margin: 0;
padding: 0;
list-style-type: none;
font: bold 13px Verdana;
width: 170px; /* Main Menu Item widths */
border-bottom: 1px solid #ccc;
}

.sidebarmenu ul li{
position: relative;
}

/* Top level menu links style */
.sidebarmenu ul li a{
display: block;
overflow: auto; /*force hasLayout in IE7 */
color: white;
text-decoration: none;
padding: 6px;
border-bottom: 1px solid #778;
border-right: 1px solid #778;
}

.sidebarmenu ul li a:link, .sidebarmenu ul li a:visited, .sidebarmenu ul li
a:active{
background-color:#071D7D; /*background of tabs (default state)*/
}

.sidebarmenu ul li a:visited{
color: white;
}

.sidebarmenu ul li a:hover{
background-color: black;
}

/*Sub level menu items */
.sidebarmenu ul li ul{
position: absolute;

```

```

width: 170px; /*Sub Menu Items width */
top: 0;
visibility: hidden;
}

.sidebarmenu a.subfolderstyle{
background: url(right.gif) no-repeat 97% 50%;
}

/* Holly Hack for IE */
* html .sidebarmenu ul li { float: left; height: 1%; }
* html .sidebarmenu ul li a { height: 1%; }
/* End */
<style type="text/css">

/*Credits: Dynamic Drive CSS Library */
/*URL: http://www.dynamicdrive.com/style/ */

#ddblueblockmenu{
border: 1px solid black;
border-bottom-width: 0;
width: 185px;
}

#ddblueblockmenu ul{
margin: 0;
padding: 0;
list-style-type: none;
font: normal 90% 'Trebuchet MS', 'Lucida Grande', Arial, sans-serif;
}

#ddblueblockmenu li a{
display: block;
padding: 3px 0;
padding-left: 0px;
width: 169px; /*185px minus all left/right paddings and margins*/
text-decoration: none;
color: white;
background-color: #2175bc;
border-bottom: 1px solid #90bade;
border-left: 7px solid #1958b7;
}

* html #ddblueblockmenu li a{ /*IE only */
width: 187px; /*IE 5*/
width: 169px; /*185px minus all left/right paddings and margins*/
}

#ddblueblockmenu li a:hover {
background-color: #2586d7;
border-left-color: #1c64d1;
}

#ddblueblockmenu div.menutitle{
color: white;
border-bottom: 1px solid black;

```

```

padding: 1px 0;
padding-left: 0px;
background-color: black;
font: bold 90% 'Trebuchet MS', 'Lucida Grande', Arial, sans-serif;
}

</style>

<script type="text/javascript">

//Nested Side Bar Menu (Mar 20th, 09)
//By Dynamic Drive: http://www.dynamicdrive.com/style/

var menuids=["sidebarmenu1"] //Enter id(s) of each Side Bar Menu's main UL,
separated by commas

function initsidebarmenu(){
for (var i=0; i<menuids.length; i++){
var ultags=document.getElementById(menuids[i]).getElementsByTagName("ul")
for (var t=0; t<ultags.length; t++){
ultags[t].parentNode.getElementsByTagName("a")[0].className+="
subfolderstyle"
if (ultags[t].parentNode.parentNode.id==menuids[i]) //if this is a first
level submenu
ultags[t].style.left=ultags[t].parentNode.offsetWidth+"px" //dynamically
position first level submenus to be width of main menu item
else //else if this is a sub level submenu (ul)
ultags[t].style.left=ultags[t-
1].getElementsByTagName("a")[0].offsetWidth+"px" //position menu to the right
of menu item that activated it
ultags[t].parentNode.onmouseover=function(){
this.getElementsByTagName("ul")[0].style.display="block"
}
ultags[t].parentNode.onmouseout=function(){
this.getElementsByTagName("ul")[0].style.display="none"
}
}
for (var t=ultags.length-1; t>-1; t--){ //loop through all sub menus again,
and use "display:none" to hide menus (to prevent possible page scrollbars
ultags[t].style.visibility="visible"
ultags[t].style.display="none"
}
}
}

if (window.addEventListener)
window.addEventListener("load", initsidebarmenu, false)
else if (window.attachEvent)
window.attachEvent("onload", initsidebarmenu)

</script>

<!-- sliderman.js -->
<script type="text/javascript" src="img/sliderman.1.2.1.js"></script>

```

```
<link rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" href="img/sliderman.css" />
<!-- /sliderman.js -->
```

```
<style type="text/css">.A {
    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; FONT-SIZE: 11px; FONT-FAMILY: Verdana,Arial; TEXT-
ALIGN: left; TEXT-DECORATION: none
}
.A:link {
    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #808080; TEXT-DECORATION: none
}
.A:visited {
    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #808080; TEXT-DECORATION: none
}
.A:hover {
    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #000080
}
.A:active {
    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #000080
}
.B {
    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; FONT-SIZE: 11px; FONT-FAMILY: Verdana,Arial; TEXT-
ALIGN: left; TEXT-DECORATION: none
}
.B:link {
    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #ffffcc; TEXT-DECORATION: none
}
.B:visited {
    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #ffffcc; TEXT-DECORATION: none
}
.B:hover {
```

```

        FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: Black
    }
    .B:active {
        FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #000080
    }

    .style1
    {
        width: 602px;
    }
</style>

<!--
text-align:center
font-style:oblique
font-size:16;
word-spacing:3em;letter-spacing:1em;text-transform:uppercase;vertical-
align:super;line-height:120%
-->

</head>
<body style="background-color:White" onload="Carousel()">
    <form id="form1" runat="server">

        <div>
            <table border="0" cellpadding="0" width="100%" cellspacing="0">
                <tr>

                    <td style="background-color:#071D7D;
color:White; size:50%">

                    <h1/><center /><strong />Time Series
Forecast

                    </td>

                    <td style="background-color:#071D7D;
size:5%">

```

```

                                <!---->
                                <table align="right"><tr ><td
valign="top">
                                <a
href="javascript:gotoshow()"></a>
                                <script>
                                <!--
//configure the paths of the images, plus corresponding target links
slideshowimages("images/pic1.jpg","images/pic2.jpg","images/pic3.jpg")
//slideshowlinks("http://food.epicurious.com/run/recipe/view?id=13285","http:
//food.epicurious.com/run/recipe/view?id=10092","http://food.epicurious.com/r
un/recipe/view?id=100975","http://food.epicurious.com/run/recipe/view?id=2876
","http://food.epicurious.com/run/recipe/view?id=20010")
//configure the speed of the slideshow, in miliseconds
var slideshowspeed=4000
var whichlink=0
var whichimage=0
function slideit(){
if (!document.images)
return
document.images.slide.src=slideimages[whichimage].src
whichlink=whichimage
if (whichimage<slideimages.length-1)
whichimage++
else
whichimage=0
setTimeout("slideit()",slideshowspeed)
}
slideit()
function btnSignIn_onclick() {
}
//-->
</script>
</table>
                                </td>
                                </tr>
                                </table>
                                </td>
                                </tr>
                                </table>
                                </td>
                                </tr>
                                </table>
                                </td>
                                </tr>
                                <tr valign="top">
                                <td colspan="3" valign="top"><div>
                                <ul class="glossymenu" style="width=100%">

```



```

        <asp:DropDownList runat="server" ID="ddl1"><asp:ListItem
Text="Individual" Value="indi" ></asp:ListItem><asp:ListItem Text="Agency"
></asp:ListItem><asp:ListItem Text="Company">
        </asp:ListItem></asp:DropDownList>
        </td>
        </tr>
        <tr>
        <td>

        </td>
        <td>
        <asp:Button ID="btnSignIn" runat="server" Text="Sign In"
onclick="btnSignIn_Click1"
        />

        </td>

        </td>
        </tr>
</table>

        </td>
        </tr>
</table>

        </td></tr>

        <tr><td style="padding-top:5px">

        <asp:Label ID="Label1"
runat="server" Text="Label"></asp:Label>

        </td></tr>
</tbody></table>
</td>
        <td valign="top" class="style1">
        <table align="left" border="2" style="border-
color:Blue" height="500px" width="100%">
        <tr style="height:5px">
        <td width="100%" valign="top"
style="background-color:#071D7D;color:White;height:5px;font-weight:bold">
                Home                <tr
style="height:580px">
        <td valign="top" align="left" style="font-
size:large; padding-left:10px;padding-right:10px;color:Black">
                <br /><FONT style="FONT-FAMILY: Verdana;
COLOR: #993300; FONT-SIZE: 16px;font-weight:bold"> Welcome to Time Series
Forecast.</font><BR><br />

```



```

                <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:10px">
                    <td valign="top" align="center"
style="padding-top:10px">
                        
                    </tr>
                    <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
                        <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-
Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Xanther stocks,USA</td>
                    </tr>
                    <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:20px">
                        <td valign="top" align="center"
style="padding-top:10px">
                            
                    </tr>
                    <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
                        <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-
Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Monger stocks talks, UK</td>
                    </tr>
                </table>
            </td></tr></table>
</td>--%>
</tr></table></td>
    </tr>
</table>
    </td>
</tr>
</table></div>
<!--<table align="left" border="1">
<tr align="left">
<td align="left">
<script type="text/javascript">

/*****
* Carousel Slideshow script- © Ger Versluis 2003
* Permission granted to DynamicDrive.com to feature script
* This notice must stay intact for legal use
* Visit http://www.dynamicdrive.com/ for full source code
*****/

/*****
Create a div with transparent place holder in your html
<div id="Carousel" style="position:relative">
    
</div>
placeholder width:
    4 sided: 1.42 * carousel image width + 3
    6 sided: 2 * carousel image width +4
    8 sided: 2.62 * carousel image width + 5
    12 sided: 3.87 * carousel image width + 7

```

```

placeholder height:
    carousel image height+2

Insert onload in body tag
    <body onload="Carousel()">
*****/

// 7 variables to control behavior
var Car_Image_Width=402;
var Car_Image_Height=202;
var Car_Border=true;           // true or false
var Car_Border_Color="white";
var Car_Speed=4;
var Car_Direction=true;       // true or false
var Car_NoOfSides=8;          // must be 4, 6, 8 or 12

/* array to specify images and optional links.
For 4 sided carousel specify at least 2 images
For 6 sided carousel specify at least 3
For 8 sided carousel specify at least 4
For 12 sided carousel specify at least 6
If Link is not needed keep it ""
*/
Car_Image_Sources=new Array(
    "images/a.jpg","",
    "images/b.jpg","",
    "images/c.jpg","", //this slide isn't linked
    "images/d.jpg","", // NOTE No comma after last line
);

/***** DO NOT EDIT BELOW *****/
CW_I=new Array(Car_NoOfSides/2+1);C_ClcW=new Array(Car_NoOfSides/2);
C_Coef=new Array(
    3*Math.PI/2,0,3*Math.PI/2,11*Math.PI/6,Math.PI/6,3*Math.PI/2,7*Math.PI/
4, 0,
    Math.PI/4,3*Math.PI/2,5*Math.PI/3,11*Math.PI/6,0,Math.PI/6,Math.PI/3);
var
C_CoefOf=Car_NoOfSides==4?0:Car_NoOfSides==6?2:Car_NoOfSides==8?5:9;
C_Pre_Img=new Array(Car_Image_Sources.length);
var
C_Angle=Car_Direction?Math.PI/(Car_NoOfSides/2):0,C_CrImg=Car_NoOfSides,C_Max
W,C_TotalW,
C_Stppd=false,i,C_LeftOffset,C_HalfNo=Car_NoOfSides/2;

function Carousel(){
    if(document.getElementById){
        for(i=0;i<Car_Image_Sources.length;i+=2){
            C_Pre_Img[i]=new
Image();C_Pre_Img[i].src=Car_Image_Sources[i]}

C_MaxW=Car_Image_Width/Math.sin(Math.PI/Car_NoOfSides)+C_HalfNo+1;
Car_Div=document.getElementById("Carousel");
for(i=0;i<C_HalfNo;i++){

```

```

CW_I[i]=document.createElement("img");Car_Div.appendChild(CW_I[i]);
    CW_I[i].style.position="absolute";
    CW_I[i].style.top=0+"px";
    CW_I[i].style.height=Car_Image_Height+"px";
    if(Car_Border){
        CW_I[i].style.borderStyle="solid";
        CW_I[i].style.borderWidth=1+"px";
        CW_I[i].style.borderColor=Car_Border_Color}
    CW_I[i].src=Car_Image_Sources[2*i];
    CW_I[i].lnk=Car_Image_Sources[2*i+1];
    CW_I[i].onclick=C_LdLnk;
    CW_I[i].onmouseover=C_Stp;
    CW_I[i].onmouseout=C_Rstrt}
    CarImages()}}

function CarImages(){
    if(!C_Stppd){
        C_TotalW=0;
        for(i=0;i<C_HalfNo;i++){

            C_ClcW[i]=Math.round(Math.cos(Math.abs(C_Coef[C_CoefOf+i]+C_Angle))*Car
_Image_Width);

            C_TotalW+=C_ClcW[i]}
        C_LeftOffset=(C_MaxW-C_TotalW)/2;
        for(i=0;i<C_HalfNo;i++){
            CW_I[i].style.left=C_LeftOffset+"px";
            CW_I[i].style.width=C_ClcW[i]+"px";
            C_LeftOffset+=C_ClcW[i]}
        C_Angle+=Car_Speed/720*Math.PI*(Car_Direction?-1:1);

        if((Car_Direction&&C_Angle<=0)||(!Car_Direction&&C_Angle>=Math.PI/C_Hal
fNo)){

            if(C_CrImg==Car_Image_Sources.length)C_CrImg=0;
            if(Car_Direction){
                CW_I[C_HalfNo]=CW_I[0];
                for(i=0;i<C_HalfNo;i++)CW_I[i]=CW_I[i+1];
                CW_I[C_HalfNo-
1].src=Car_Image_Sources[C_CrImg];
                CW_I[C_HalfNo-
1].lnk=Car_Image_Sources[C_CrImg+1]}
            else{ for(i=C_HalfNo;i>0;i--)CW_I[i]=CW_I[i-1];
                CW_I[0]=CW_I[C_HalfNo];
                CW_I[0].src=Car_Image_Sources[C_CrImg];
                CW_I[0].lnk=Car_Image_Sources[C_CrImg+1]}
            C_Angle=Car_Direction?Math.PI/C_HalfNo:0;C_CrImg+=2}}
        setTimeout("CarImages()",50)}

    function C_LdLnk(){if(this.lnk>window.location.href=this.lnk)
    function
C_Stp(){this.style.cursor=this.lnk?"pointer":"default";C_Stppd=true;}
    function C_Rstrt(){C_Stppd=false}
</script>
</td></tr></table>

<table border="1"><tr><td><div id="Carousel" style="position:relative">


```

```

</div></td></tr></table>-->
    <%--<div>
    <div id="carousel">
    <div><a href="#"></a></div>

    <div><a href="#"></a></div>

    <div><a href="#"></a></div>

    <div><a href="#"></a></div>

    <div><a href="#"></a></div>

    <div><a href="#"></a></div>
</div>--%>
    </div>
    </form>
</body>
</html>

```

Server side:

```

using System;
using System.Data;
using System.Configuration;
using System.Collections;
using System.Web;
using System.Web.Security;
using System.Web.UI;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls.WebParts;
using System.Web.UI.HtmlControls;
using System.Data.SqlClient;

public partial class Index : System.Web.UI.Page
{
    protected void Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {

    }

    protected void btnSignIn_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        SqlConnection con = new
SqlConnection("Server=Personalpc;Database=suresh;Trusted_Connection=True");
        try
        {
            con.Open();
            String Sqquery = "select count(*) from login where User_Name =' " +
txtUserName.Text + "' and Password=' " + txtPassword.Text + "'";
            SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand(Sqquery, con);
            int iRtn = (int)cmd.ExecuteScalar();//.ExecuteNonQuery();
            if (iRtn == 0)
            {
                Labell1.Text = "Invalid Username and Password";
            }
        }
    }
}

```

```

    }
    else
    {
        Session["UserName"] = txtUserName.Text;
        Response.Redirect("Dataset.aspx");
    }

}
catch (Exception ex)
{
    Response.Write(ex.Message);
}
finally
{
    con.Close();
}
}
protected void btnSignIn_Click1(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    SqlConnection con = new
SqlConnection("Server=Personalpc;Database=suresh;Trusted_Connection=True");
    try
    {
        con.Open();
        String Sqquery = "select count(*) from login where User_Name='" +
txtUserName.Text + "' and Password='" + txtPassword.Text + "'";
        SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand(Sqquery, con);
        Response.Redirect("Dataset.aspx");
        //int iRtn = (int)cmd.ExecuteScalar();//.ExecuteNonQuery();
        //if (iRtn == 0)
        //{
        //    Label1.Text = "Invalid Username and Password";
        //}
        //else
        //{
        //    Session["UserName"] = txtUserName.Text;
        //    Response.Redirect("Dataset.aspx");
        //}

    }
    catch (Exception ex)
    {
        Response.Write(ex.Message);
    }
    finally
    {
        con.Close();
    }
}
}

```

Index.aspx:

Client

```
<%@ Page Language="C#" AutoEventWireup="true" CodeFile="Index.aspx.cs"
Inherits="Index" %>

<!DOCTYPE html PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD XHTML 1.0 Transitional//EN"
"http://www.w3.org/TR/xhtml1/DTD/xhtml1-transitional.dtd">

<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml">
<head id="Head1" runat="server">
  <title>Welcome!</title>
  <!-- slideshow---***** 3d*****-->
  <script type="text/javascript" language="javascript">
    function Check()
    {
      if(document.getElementById("txtUserName").value == "")
      {
        alert("Please Enter AccountNo.");
        return false;
      }

      if(document.getElementById("txtPassword").value == "")
      {
        alert("Please Enter Mobile No.");
        return false;
      }

      if(document.getElementById("txtUserName").value == "admin" &&
document.getElementById("txtPassword").value == "admin")
      {
        location.href="Billing.aspx";
      }
      else
      {
        alert("Please enter correct username and password");
      }

      return true;

      alert("Amount Payed Successfully");
      location.href="Billing.aspx";

      return true;

    }
  </script>
  <style type="text/css">
```

```

#carousel{

    width:900px;
    height:200px;
    position:relative;
    border:0px ;
}

/*img{
    width:100%;
    height:100%;
    border:0px ;
}*/

</style>
<script src="menu/mootools.js" type="text/javascript"></script>

<script src="menu/3dcarousel.js" type="text/javascript"></script>

<style type="text/css">

/*Credits: By Santosh Setty (http://webdesigninfo.wordpress.com) */
/*Posted to: Dynamic Drive CSS Library (http://www.dynamicdrive.com/style/)
*/

.glossymenu{
    position: relative;
    padding: 0 0 0 10px;
    margin: 0 auto 0 auto;
    background: url(menu/menub_bg.gif) repeat-x; /*tab background image
path*/
    height: 46px;
    list-style: none;
}

.glossymenu li{
    float:left;
}

.glossymenu li a{
    float: left;
    display: block;
    color:#000;
    text-decoration: none;
    font-family: sans-serif;
    font-size: 15px;
    font-weight: bold;
    padding:0 0 0 18px; /*Padding to accomodate left tab image. Do not
change*/
    height: 46px;
    line-height: 46px;
    text-align: center;
    cursor: pointer;
}

.glossymenu li a b{
    float: left;
}

```

```

        display: block;
        padding: 0 20px 0 20px; /*Padding of menu items*/
    }

.glossymenu li.current a, .glossymenu li a:hover{
    color: #fff;
    background: url(menu/menub_hover_left.gif) no-repeat; /*left tab image
path*/
    background-position: left;
}

.glossymenu li.current a b, .glossymenu li a:hover b{
    color: #fff;
    background: url(menu/menub_hover_right.gif) no-repeat right top;
/*right tab image path*/
}

</style>
<script type="text/javascript" language="JavaScript1.1">
<!--

/*
JavaScript Image slideshow:
By (www.wsabstract.com)
Over 200+ free JavaScript here!
*/

var slideimages=new Array()
var slidelinks=new Array()
function slideshowimages(){
for (i=0;i<slideshowimages.arguments.length;i++){
slideimages[i]=new Image()
slideimages[i].src=slideshowimages.arguments[i]
}
}

function slideshowlinks(){
for (i=0;i<slideshowlinks.arguments.length;i++)
slidelinks[i]=slideshowlinks.arguments[i]
}

function gotoshow(){
if (!window.winslide||winslide.closed)
winslide=window.open(slidelinks[whichlink])
else
winslide.location=slidelinks[whichlink]
winslide.focus()
}

//-->
</script>
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=iso-8859-1"
/>

<meta name="description" content="2011 International Conference on Computing
and Computer Vision" />

```

```

<meta content="Ziad Kobti" name="Author" />

<meta http-equiv="Content-Style-Type" content="text/css" />
<meta content="MSHTML 6.00.6000.16735" name="GENERATOR" />

    <meta http-equiv="content-type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
    <meta http-equiv="imagetoolbar" content="no" />
    <meta name="keywords" content="slideman, sliderman.js, javascript
slider, jquery, slideshow, effects" />
    <meta name="description" content="Sliderman.js - will do all the
sliding for you :)" />
    <style type="text/css">
        * { margin: 0; outline: none; }
        body { background-color: #444444; }
        .c { clear: both; }
        #wrapper { margin: 0 auto; width: 560px; }
        h2 { font-size: 24px; line-height: 40px; font-weight: normal;
color: #adc276; text-shadow: 0 1px 3px #222222; }
    </style>
    <style type="text/css">

/*Credits: Dynamic Drive CSS Library */
/*URL: http://www.dynamicdrive.com/style/ */

.sidebarmenu ul{
margin: 0;
padding: 0;
list-style-type: none;
font: bold 13px Verdana;
width: 170px; /* Main Menu Item widths */
border-bottom: 1px solid #ccc;
}

.sidebarmenu ul li{
position: relative;
}

/* Top level menu links style */
.sidebarmenu ul li a{
display: block;
overflow: auto; /*force hasLayout in IE7 */
color: white;
text-decoration: none;
padding: 6px;
border-bottom: 1px solid #778;
border-right: 1px solid #778;
}

.sidebarmenu ul li a:link, .sidebarmenu ul li a:visited, .sidebarmenu ul li
a:active{
background-color:#071D7D; /*background of tabs (default state)*/
}

.sidebarmenu ul li a:visited{
color: white;

```

```

}

.sidebarmenu ul li a:hover{
background-color: black;
}

/*Sub level menu items */
.sidebarmenu ul li ul{
position: absolute;
width: 170px; /*Sub Menu Items width */
top: 0;
visibility: hidden;
}

.sidebarmenu a.subfolderstyle{
background: url(right.gif) no-repeat 97% 50%;
}

/* Holly Hack for IE */
* html .sidebarmenu ul li { float: left; height: 1%; }
* html .sidebarmenu ul li a { height: 1%; }
/* End */
<style type="text/css">

/*Credits: Dynamic Drive CSS Library */
/*URL: http://www.dynamicdrive.com/style/ */

#ddblueblockmenu{
border: 1px solid black;
border-bottom-width: 0;
width: 185px;
}

#ddblueblockmenu ul{
margin: 0;
padding: 0;
list-style-type: none;
font: normal 90% 'Trebuchet MS', 'Lucida Grande', Arial, sans-serif;
}

#ddblueblockmenu li a{
display: block;
padding: 3px 0;
padding-left: 0px;
width: 169px; /*185px minus all left/right paddings and margins*/
text-decoration: none;
color: white;
background-color: #2175bc;
border-bottom: 1px solid #90bade;
border-left: 7px solid #1958b7;
}

* html #ddblueblockmenu li a{ /*IE only */
width: 187px; /*IE 5*/
width: 169px; /*185px minus all left/right paddings and margins*/
}

```

```

#ddbblueblockmenu li a:hover {
background-color: #2586d7;
border-left-color: #1c64d1;
}

#ddbblueblockmenu div.menutitle{
color: white;
border-bottom: 1px solid black;
padding: 1px 0;
padding-left: 0px;
background-color: black;
font: bold 90% 'Trebuchet MS', 'Lucida Grande', Arial, sans-serif;
}

</style>

```

```
<script type="text/javascript">
```

```
//Nested Side Bar Menu (Mar 20th, 09)
```

```
//By Dynamic Drive: http://www.dynamicdrive.com/style/
```

```
var menuids=["sidebarmenu1"] //Enter id(s) of each Side Bar Menu's main UL,
separated by commas
```

```
function initsidebarmenu(){
for (var i=0; i<menuids.length; i++){
    var ultags=document.getElementById(menuids[i]).getElementsByTagName("ul")
    for (var t=0; t<ultags.length; t++){
        ultags[t].parentNode.getElementsByTagName("a")[0].className+="
subfolderstyle"
        if (ultags[t].parentNode.parentNode.id==menuids[i]) //if this is a first
level submenu
            ultags[t].style.left=ultags[t].parentNode.offsetWidth+"px" //dynamically
position first level submenus to be width of main menu item
        else //else if this is a sub level submenu (ul)
            ultags[t].style.left=ultags[t-
1].getElementsByTagName("a")[0].offsetWidth+"px" //position menu to the right
of menu item that activated it
            ultags[t].parentNode.onmouseover=function(){
                this.getElementsByTagName("ul")[0].style.display="block"
            }
            ultags[t].parentNode.onmouseout=function(){
                this.getElementsByTagName("ul")[0].style.display="none"
            }
            }
        for (var t=ultags.length-1; t>-1; t--){ //loop through all sub menus again,
and use "display:none" to hide menus (to prevent possible page scrollbars
            ultags[t].style.visibility="visible"
            ultags[t].style.display="none"
        }
    }
}
}

```

```
if (window.addEventListener)
window.addEventListener("load", initsidebarmenu, false)
else if (window.attachEvent)
window.attachEvent("onload", initsidebarmenu)

</script>

<!-- sliderman.js -->
<script type="text/javascript" src="img/sliderman.1.2.1.js"></script>
<link rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" href="img/sliderman.css" />
<!-- /sliderman.js -->

<style type="text/css">.A {

    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; FONT-SIZE: 11px; FONT-FAMILY: Verdana,Arial; TEXT-
ALIGN: left; TEXT-DECORATION: none

}

.A:link {

    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #808080; TEXT-DECORATION: none

}

.A:visited {

    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #808080; TEXT-DECORATION: none

}

.A:hover {

    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #000080

}

.A:active {

    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #000080

}

.B {

    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; FONT-SIZE: 11px; FONT-FAMILY: Verdana,Arial; TEXT-
ALIGN: left; TEXT-DECORATION: none

}

.B:link {

    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #ffffcc; TEXT-DECORATION: none
```

```
}

.B:visited {
    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #ffffcc; TEXT-DECORATION: none
}

.B:hover {
    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: Black
}

.B:active {
    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #000080
}

.style1
{
    width: 602px;
}

.style2
{
    width: 171px;
}

.style3
{
    width: 134px;
}

</style>

<!--
text-align:center
font-style:oblique
font-size:16;
word-spacing:3em;letter-spacing:1em;text-transform:uppercase;vertical-
align:super;line-height:120%
-->

</head>
<body style="background-color:White" onload="Carousel()">
    <form id="form1" runat="server">

    <div>
    <table border="0" cellpadding="0" width="100%" cellspacing="0">
        <tr>
```

```

                                <td style="background-color:#071D7D;
color:White; size:50%">

                                <h1/><center /><strong />Time Series
Forecast

                                </td>

                                <td style="background-color:#071D7D;
size:5%">

                                <!---->

                                <table align="right"><tr ><td
valign="top">

                                <a
href="javascript:gotoshow()"></a>
<script>
<!--

//configure the paths of the images, plus corresponding target links
slideshowimages("images/pic1.jpg","images/pic2.jpg","images/pic3.jpg")
//slideshowlinks("http://food.epicurious.com/run/recipe/view?id=13285","http:
//food.epicurious.com/run/recipe/view?id=10092","http://food.epicurious.com/r
un/recipe/view?id=100975","http://food.epicurious.com/run/recipe/view?id=2876
","http://food.epicurious.com/run/recipe/view?id=20010")

//configure the speed of the slideshow, in miliseconds
var slideshowspeed=4000

var whichlink=0
var whichimage=0
function slideit(){
if (!document.images)
return
document.images.slide.src=slideimages[whichimage].src
whichlink=whichimage
if (whichimage<slideimages.length-1)
whichimage++
else
whichimage=0
setTimeout("slideit()",slideshowspeed)
}
slideit()

//-->
</script>

```

```

</table>
        </td>
    </tr>
</table>
</td>
</tr>

</table>

    </td>
</tr>
<tr valign="top">
    <td colspan="3" valign="top"><div>
<ul class="glossymenu" style="width=100%">
    <li ><a href="Home.aspx"><b>Home</b></a></li>
    <li ><a href="Dataset.aspx"><b>Dataset</b></a></li>
    <li class="current"><a href="Index.aspx"><b>Index</b></a></li>
    <li><a href="Cluster.aspx"><b>Cluster</b></a></li>
    <li><a href="Weight.aspx"><b>Weight</b></a></li>
    <li><a href="Forecast.aspx"><b>Forecast</b></a></li>
</ul></div></td>
    </tr>
    <tr valign="top">
        <td valign="top"><table cellpadding="0" style="vertical-align:top" cellspacing="5" border="0" ><tr valign="top">
            <td valign="top" width="12%">

                <table border="2" style="border-color:Blue">
                    <tr style="height:6px">
                        <td width="100%" style="background-color:#071D7D;color:White;height:4px;font-weight:bold">Forecasting <br />Legends</td>

                    </tr>
                    <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:20px">
                        <td valign="top" align="center" style="padding-top:10px">
                            
                        </td>
                    </tr>
                    <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
                        <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Reliable stocks,India</td>
                    </tr>
                    <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:10px">
                        <td valign="top" align="center" style="padding-top:10px">
                            
                        </td>
                    </tr>
                    <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
                        <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Xanther stocks,USA</td>
                    </tr>
                </table>
            </td>
        </tr>
    </tr>

```

```

        <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:20px">
            <td valign="top" align="center"
style="padding-top:10px">
                
            </tr>
            <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
                <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-
Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Monger stocks talks, UK</td>
            </tr>
        </table>
    </td>
        <td valign="top" class="style1">
            <table align="left" border="2" style="border-
color:Blue" height="500px" width="100%">
                <tr style="height:5px">
                    <td width="100%" valign="top"
style="background-color:#071D7D;color:White;height:5px;font-
weight:bold">Index </td>
                </tr>
                <tr style="height:580px">
                    <td valign="top" align="left" style="font-
size:large; padding-left:10px;padding-right:10px;color:Black">
                        <br /><FONT style="FONT-FAMILY: Verdana;
COLOR: #993300; FONT-SIZE: 16px;font-weight:bold"> The Index</font><BR><br />
            </td>
        </table>
    </td>
</tr>
<table border="1" style="border-color:Blue; border-
width:thick"cellspacing="3" cellpadding="3" align="center" width="100%"
style="vertical-align:right ">
<tr align="left">
<td class="style2" >The Silhouette Index</td>
    <td align="left" class="style3">
        The Dunn Index
    </td>
    <td>
        The Davies-Bouldin Index
    </td>
</tr>
<tr><td class="style2">1</td>
<td align="left" style="padding-left:10px" class="style3">
    -1
</td>
<td>
    4.0
</td>
</tr>
</table>
</td>
</table>

```

```

        </div>

    </td>

</tr>
</table>

        </td>
    </tr>
</table>
</td>

    <!--<td valign="top" width="20%">
        <table align="left" border="2" style="border-color:Blue"
height="300px" width="100%">
        <tr><td valign="top" width="25%">
            <table border="0" cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0">

                <tr style="height:6px">
                    <td width="100%" style="background-
color:#071D7D;color:White;height:4px;font-weight:bold">Forecasting    <br
/>Legends</td>

                </tr>
                <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:20px">
                    <td valign="top" align="center"
style="padding-top:10px">
                        
                    </tr>
                    <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
                        <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-
Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Reliable stocks,India</td>
                    </tr>
                    <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:10px">
                        <td valign="top" align="center"
style="padding-top:10px">
                            
                        </tr>
                        <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
                            <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-
Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Xanther stocks,USA</td>
                        </tr>
                        <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:20px">
                            <td valign="top" align="center"
style="padding-top:10px">
                                
                            </tr>
                    </tr>
                </table>
            </td>
        </tr>
    </table>
    </td>
    </tr>
</table>

```

```

        </tr>
        <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
            <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-
Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Monger stocks talks, UK</td>
        </tr>
    </table>
</td></tr></table>
</td>--%>
</tr></table></td>

```

```

    </tr>
</table>
    </td>
</tr>
</table></div>
<!--<table align="left" border="1">
<tr align="left">
<td align="left">
<script type="text/javascript">

/*****
* Carousel Slideshow script- © Ger Versluis 2003
* Permission granted to DynamicDrive.com to feature script
* This notice must stay intact for legal use
* Visit http://www.dynamicdrive.com/ for full source code
*****/

/*****
Create a div with transparent place holder in your html
<div id="Carousel" style="position:relative">
    
</div>
placeholder width:
    4 sided: 1.42 * carousel image width + 3
    6 sided: 2 * carousel image width +4
    8 sided: 2.62 * carousel image width + 5
    12 sided: 3.87 * carousel image width + 7
placeholder height:
    carousel image height+2

Insert onload in body tag
    <body onload="Carousel()">
*****/

// 7 variables to control behavior
var Car_Image_Width=402;
var Car_Image_Height=202;
var Car_Border=true;           // true or false
var Car_Border_Color="white";
var Car_Speed=4;
var Car_Direction=true;       // true or false
var Car_NoOfSides=8;          // must be 4, 6, 8 or 12

```

```

/* array to specify images and optional links.
   For 4 sided carousel specify at least 2 images
   For 6 sided carousel specify at least 3
   For 8 sided carousel specify at least 4
   For 12 sided carousel specify at least 6
   If Link is not needed keep it ""
*/
   Car_Image_Sources=new Array(
       "images/a.jpg","",
       "images/b.jpg","",
       "images/c.jpg","", //this slide isn't linked
       "images/d.jpg",""// NOTE No comma after last line
   );

/***** DO NOT EDIT BELOW *****/
   CW_I=new Array(Car_NoOfSides/2+1);C_ClcW=new Array(Car_NoOfSides/2);
   C_Coef=new Array(
4,
       3*Math.PI/2,0,3*Math.PI/2,11*Math.PI/6,Math.PI/6,3*Math.PI/2,7*Math.PI/
0,
       Math.PI/4,3*Math.PI/2,5*Math.PI/3,11*Math.PI/6,0,Math.PI/6,Math.PI/3);
   var
C_CoefOf=Car_NoOfSides==4?0:Car_NoOfSides==6?2:Car_NoOfSides==8?5:9;
   C_Pre_Img=new Array(Car_Image_Sources.length);
   var
C_Angle=Car_Direction?Math.PI/(Car_NoOfSides/2):0,C_CrImg=Car_NoOfSides,C_Max
W,C_TotalW,
   C_Stppd=false,i,C_LeftOffset,C_HalfNo=Car_NoOfSides/2;

   function Carousel(){
       if(document.getElementById){
           for(i=0;i<Car_Image_Sources.length;i+=2){
               C_Pre_Img[i]=new
Image();C_Pre_Img[i].src=Car_Image_Sources[i]}

   C_MaxW=Car_Image_Width/Math.sin(Math.PI/Car_NoOfSides)+C_HalfNo+1;
       Car_Div=document.getElementById("Carousel");
       for(i=0;i<C_HalfNo;i++){

   CW_I[i]=document.createElement("img");Car_Div.appendChild(CW_I[i]);
       CW_I[i].style.position="absolute";
       CW_I[i].style.top=0+"px";
       CW_I[i].style.height=Car_Image_Height+"px";
       if(Car_Border){
           CW_I[i].style.borderStyle="solid";
           CW_I[i].style.borderWidth=1+"px";
           CW_I[i].style.borderColor=Car_Border_Color}
       CW_I[i].src=Car_Image_Sources[2*i];
       CW_I[i].lnk=Car_Image_Sources[2*i+1];
       CW_I[i].onclick=C_LdLnk;
       CW_I[i].onmouseover=C_Stp;
       CW_I[i].onmouseout=C_Rstrt}
   CarImages()}}

```

```

function CarImages () {
    if(!C_Stppd) {
        C_TotalW=0;
        for(i=0;i<C_HalfNo;i++) {

            C_ClcW[i]=Math.round(Math.cos(Math.abs(C_Coef[C_CoefOf+i]+C_Angle))*Car
_Image_Width);

            C_TotalW+=C_ClcW[i]}
        C_LeftOffset=(C_MaxW-C_TotalW)/2;
        for(i=0;i<C_HalfNo;i++) {
            CW_I[i].style.left=C_LeftOffset+"px";
            CW_I[i].style.width=C_ClcW[i]+"px";
            C_LeftOffset+=C_ClcW[i]}
        C_Angle+=Car_Speed/720*Math.PI*(Car_Direction?-1:1);

        if((Car_Direction&&C_Angle<=0)||(!Car_Direction&&C_Angle>=Math.PI/C_Hal
fNo)) {
            if(C_CrImg==Car_Image_Sources.length)C_CrImg=0;
            if(Car_Direction) {
                CW_I[C_HalfNo]=CW_I[0];
                for(i=0;i<C_HalfNo;i++)CW_I[i]=CW_I[i+1];
                CW_I[C_HalfNo-
1].src=Car_Image_Sources[C_CrImg];
                CW_I[C_HalfNo-
1].lnk=Car_Image_Sources[C_CrImg+1]}
            else{ for(i=C_HalfNo;i>0;i--)CW_I[i]=CW_I[i-1];
                CW_I[0]=CW_I[C_HalfNo];
                CW_I[0].src=Car_Image_Sources[C_CrImg];
                CW_I[0].lnk=Car_Image_Sources[C_CrImg+1]}
            C_Angle=Car_Direction*Math.PI/C_HalfNo:0;C_CrImg+=2}}
        setTimeout("CarImages()",50)}

        function C_LdLnk(){if(this.lnk>window.location.href=this.lnk)
        function
C_Stp(){this.style.cursor=this.lnk?"pointer":"default";C_Stppd=true;}
        function C_Rstrt(){C_Stppd=false}
    </script>
</td></tr></table>

    <table border="1"><tr><td><div id="Carousel" style="position:relative">

</div></td></tr></table>-->
    <%--<div>
    <div id="carousel">
    <div><a href="#"></a></div>

    <div><a href="#"></a></div>

    <div><a href="#"></a></div>

    <div><a href="#"></a></div>

    <div><a href="#"></a></div>

    <div><a href="#"></a></div>
</div>-->
    </div>

```

```
</form>
</body>
</html>
```

Cluster.aspx

Client side

```
<%@ Page Language="C#" AutoEventWireup="true" CodeFile="Cluster.aspx.cs"
Inherits="Cluster" %>

<!DOCTYPE html PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD XHTML 1.0 Transitional//EN"
"http://www.w3.org/TR/xhtml1/DTD/xhtml1-transitional.dtd">

<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml">
<head id="Head1" runat="server">
  <title>Welcome!</title>
  <!-- slideshow---***** 3d*****-->
  <script type="text/javascript" language="javascript">
    function Check()
    {
      if(document.getElementById("txtUserName").value == "")
      {
        alert("Please Enter name");
        return false;
      }

      if(document.getElementById("txtPassword").value == "")
      {
        alert("Please Enter password");
        return false;
      }

      if(document.getElementById("txtUserName").value == "admin" &&
document.getElementById("txtPassword").value == "admin")
      {
        location.href="Billing.aspx";
      }
      else
      {
        alert("Please enter correct username and password");
      }
    }
  </script>
</head>
<body>
  <div style="text-align: center;">
    <h1>Welcome!</h1>
    <div style="display: inline-block; width: 40%; text-align: left; vertical-align: top; margin-right: 10px;">
      <input type="text" value="Username" />
      <input type="password" value="Password" />
      <input type="button" value="Login" />
    </div>
  </div>
</body>
</html>
```

```

    }

    return true;

    alert("Amount Payed Successfully");
    location.href="Billing.aspx";

    return true;

}
</script>
<style type="text/css">
#carousel{

    width:900px;
    height:200px;
    position:relative;
    border:0px ;
}

/*img{
    width:100%;
    height:100%;
    border:0px ;
}*/

</style>
<script src="menu/mootools.js" type="text/javascript"></script>

<script src="menu/3dcarousel.js" type="text/javascript"></script>

<style type="text/css">

/*Credits: By Santosh Setty (http://webdesigninfo.wordpress.com) */
/*Posted to: Dynamic Drive CSS Library (http://www.dynamicdrive.com/style/)
*/

.glossymenu{
    position: relative;
    padding: 0 0 0 10px;
    margin: 0 auto 0 auto;
    background: url(menu/menub_bg.gif) repeat-x; /*tab background image
path*/
    height: 46px;
    list-style: none;
}

.glossymenu li{
    float:left;
}

.glossymenu li a{
    float: left;
    display: block;

```

```

        color:#000;
        text-decoration: none;
        font-family: sans-serif;
        font-size: 15px;
        font-weight: bold;
        padding:0 0 0 18px; /*Padding to accomodate left tab image. Do not
change*/
        height: 46px;
        line-height: 46px;
        text-align: center;
        cursor: pointer;
    }

.glossymenu li a b{
    float: left;
    display: block;
    padding: 0 20px 0 20px; /*Padding of menu items*/
}

.glossymenu li.current a, .glossymenu li a:hover{
    color: #fff;
    background: url(menu/menub_hover_left.gif) no-repeat; /*left tab image
path*/
    background-position: left;
}

.glossymenu li.current a b, .glossymenu li a:hover b{
    color: #fff;
    background: url(menu/menub_hover_right.gif) no-repeat right top;
/*right tab image path*/
}

</style>
<script type="text/javascript" language="JavaScript1.1">
<!--

/*
JavaScript Image slideshow:
By (www.wsabstract.com)
Over 200+ free JavaScript here!
*/

var slideimages=new Array()
var slidelinks=new Array()
function slideshowimages(){
for (i=0;i<slideshowimages.arguments.length;i++){
slideimages[i]=new Image()
slideimages[i].src=slideshowimages.arguments[i]
}
}

function slideshowlinks(){
for (i=0;i<slideshowlinks.arguments.length;i++)
slidelinks[i]=slideshowlinks.arguments[i]
}

```

```

function gotoshow(){
if (!window.winslide||winslide.closed)
winslide=window.open(slidelinks[whichlink])
else
winslide.location=slidelinks[whichlink]
winslide.focus()
}

//-->
</script>
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=iso-8859-1"
/>

<meta name="description" content="2011 International Conference on Computing
and Computer Vision" />

<meta content="Ziad Kobti" name="Author" />

<meta http-equiv="Content-Style-Type" content="text/css" />
<meta content="MSHTML 6.00.6000.16735" name="GENERATOR" />

<meta http-equiv="content-type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
<meta http-equiv="imagetoolbar" content="no" />
<meta name="keywords" content="slideman, sliderman.js, javascript
slider, jquery, slideshow, effects" />
<meta name="description" content="Sliderman.js - will do all the
sliding for you :)" />
<style type="text/css">
* { margin: 0; outline: none; }
body { background-color: #444444; }
.c { clear: both; }
#wrapper { margin: 0 auto; width: 560px; }
h2 { font-size: 24px; line-height: 40px; font-weight: normal;
color: #adc276; text-shadow: 0 1px 3px #222222; }
</style>
<style type="text/css">

/*Credits: Dynamic Drive CSS Library */
/*URL: http://www.dynamicdrive.com/style/ */

.sidebarmenu ul{
margin: 0;
padding: 0;
list-style-type: none;
font: bold 13px Verdana;
width: 170px; /* Main Menu Item widths */
border-bottom: 1px solid #ccc;
}

.sidebarmenu ul li{
position: relative;
}

/* Top level menu links style */
.sidebarmenu ul li a{
display: block;

```

```

overflow: auto; /*force hasLayout in IE7 */
color: white;
text-decoration: none;
padding: 6px;
border-bottom: 1px solid #778;
border-right: 1px solid #778;
}

.sidebarmenu ul li a:link, .sidebarmenu ul li a:visited, .sidebarmenu ul li
a:active{
background-color:#071D7D; /*background of tabs (default state)*/
}

.sidebarmenu ul li a:visited{
color: white;
}

.sidebarmenu ul li a:hover{
background-color: black;
}

/*Sub level menu items */
.sidebarmenu ul li ul{
position: absolute;
width: 170px; /*Sub Menu Items width */
top: 0;
visibility: hidden;
}

.sidebarmenu a.subfolderstyle{
background: url(right.gif) no-repeat 97% 50%;
}

/* Holly Hack for IE */
* html .sidebarmenu ul li { float: left; height: 1%; }
* html .sidebarmenu ul li a { height: 1%; }
/* End */
<style type="text/css">

/*Credits: Dynamic Drive CSS Library */
/*URL: http://www.dynamicdrive.com/style/ */

#dblueblockmenu{
border: 1px solid black;
border-bottom-width: 0;
width: 185px;
}

#dblueblockmenu ul{
margin: 0;
padding: 0;
list-style-type: none;
font: normal 90% 'Trebuchet MS', 'Lucida Grande', Arial, sans-serif;
}

#dblueblockmenu li a{

```

```

display: block;
padding: 3px 0;
padding-left: 0px;
width: 169px; /*185px minus all left/right paddings and margins*/
text-decoration: none;
color: white;
background-color: #2175bc;
border-bottom: 1px solid #90bade;
border-left: 7px solid #1958b7;
}

* html #ddblueblockmenu li a{ /*IE only */
width: 187px; /*IE 5*/
width: 169px; /*185px minus all left/right paddings and margins*/
}

#ddblueblockmenu li a:hover {
background-color: #2586d7;
border-left-color: #1c64d1;
}

#ddblueblockmenu div.menutitle{
color: white;
border-bottom: 1px solid black;
padding: 1px 0;
padding-left: 0px;
background-color: black;
font: bold 90% 'Trebuchet MS', 'Lucida Grande', Arial, sans-serif;
}

</style>

```

```
<script type="text/javascript">
```

```
//Nested Side Bar Menu (Mar 20th, 09)
```

```
//By Dynamic Drive: http://www.dynamicdrive.com/style/
```

```
var menuids=["sidebarmenu1"] //Enter id(s) of each Side Bar Menu's main UL,
separated by commas
```

```
function initsidebarmenu(){
```

```
for (var i=0; i<menuids.length; i++){
```

```
var ultags=document.getElementById(menuids[i]).getElementsByTagName("ul")
```

```
for (var t=0; t<ultags.length; t++){
```

```
ultags[t].parentNode.getElementsByTagName("a")[0].className+="
```

```
subfolderstyle"
```

```
if (ultags[t].parentNode.parentNode.id==menuids[i]) //if this is a first
level submenu
```

```
ultags[t].style.left=ultags[t].parentNode.offsetWidth+"px" //dynamically
position first level submenus to be width of main menu item
```

```
else //else if this is a sub level submenu (ul)
```

```
ultags[t].style.left=ultags[t-
```

```
1].getElementsByTagName("a")[0].offsetWidth+"px" //position menu to the right
of menu item that activated it
```

```

    ultags[t].parentNode.onmouseover=function(){
    this.getElementsByTagName("ul")[0].style.display="block"
    }
    ultags[t].parentNode.onmouseout=function(){
    this.getElementsByTagName("ul")[0].style.display="none"
    }
    }
    for (var t=ultags.length-1; t>-1; t--){ //loop through all sub menus again,
and use "display:none" to hide menus (to prevent possible page scrollbars
    ultags[t].style.visibility="visible"
    ultags[t].style.display="none"
    }
    }
}

if (window.addEventListener)
window.addEventListener("load", initsidebarmenu, false)
else if (window.attachEvent)
window.attachEvent("onload", initsidebarmenu)

</script>

```

```

<!-- sliderman.js -->
<script type="text/javascript" src="img/sliderman.1.2.1.js"></script>
<link rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" href="img/sliderman.css" />
<!-- /sliderman.js -->

```

```

<style type="text/css">.A {

    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; FONT-SIZE: 11px; FONT-FAMILY: Verdana,Arial; TEXT-
ALIGN: left; TEXT-DECORATION: none

}

.A:link {

    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #808080; TEXT-DECORATION: none

}

.A:visited {

    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #808080; TEXT-DECORATION: none

}

.A:hover {

    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #000080

}

.A:active {

```

```
        FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #000080
    }
    .B {
        FONT-WEIGHT: bold; FONT-SIZE: 11px; FONT-FAMILY: Verdana,Arial; TEXT-
        ALIGN: left; TEXT-DECORATION: none
    }
    .B:link {
        FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #ffffcc; TEXT-DECORATION: none
    }
    .B:visited {
        FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #ffffcc; TEXT-DECORATION: none
    }
    .B:hover {
        FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: Black
    }
    .B:active {
        FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #000080
    }

    .style1
    {
        width: 602px;
    }

    .style2
    {
        width: 171px;
    }
    .style3
    {
        width: 134px;
    }

</style>

<!--
text-align:center
font-style:oblique
font-size:16;
word-spacing:3em;letter-spacing:1em;text-transform:uppercase;vertical-
align:super;line-height:120%
```

-->

```
</head>
<body style="background-color:White" onload="Carousel()">
  <form id="form1" runat="server">

    <div>
      <table border="0" cellpadding="0" width="100%" cellspacing="0">
        <tr>

          <td style="background-color:#071D7D;
color:White; size:50%">

          <h1/><center /><strong />Time Series
Forecast

          </td>

          <td style="background-color:#071D7D;
size:5%">

          <!---->

          <table align="right"><tr ><td
valign="top">

          <a
href="javascript:gotoshow()"></a>
<script>
<!--

//configure the paths of the images, plus corresponding target links
slideshowimages("images/pic1.jpg","images/pic2.jpg","images/pic3.jpg")
//slideshowlinks("http://food.epicurious.com/run/recipe/view?id=13285","http:
//food.epicurious.com/run/recipe/view?id=10092","http://food.epicurious.com/r
un/recipe/view?id=100975","http://food.epicurious.com/run/recipe/view?id=2876
","http://food.epicurious.com/run/recipe/view?id=20010")

//configure the speed of the slideshow, in miliseconds
var slideshowspeed=4000

var whichlink=0
var whichimage=0
```

```

function slideit(){
if (!document.images)
return
document.images.slide.src=slideimages[whichimage].src
whichlink=whichimage
if (whichimage<slideimages.length-1)
whichimage++
else
whichimage=0
setTimeout("slideit()",slideshowspeed)
}
slideit()

//-->
</script>
</table>

</td>
</tr>
</table>
</td>
</tr>

</table>

</td>
</tr>
<tr valign="top">
<td colspan="3" valign="top"><div>
<ul class="glossymenu" style="width=100%">
<li ><a href="Home.aspx"><b>Home</b></a></li>
<li ><a href="Dataset.aspx"><b>Dataset</b></a></li>
<li ><a href="Index.aspx"><b>Index</b></a></li>
<li class="current"><a href="Cluster.aspx"><b>Cluster</b></a></li>
<li ><a href="Weight.aspx"><b>Weight</b></a></li>
<li ><a href="Forecast.aspx"><b>Forecast</b></a></li>

</ul></div></td>
</tr>
<tr valign="top">
<td valign="top"><table cellpadding="0" style="vertical-align:top" cellspacing="5" border="0" ><tr valign="top">
<td valign="top" width="12%">

<table border="2" style="border-color:Blue">
<tr style="height:6px">
<td width="100%" style="background-color:#071D7D;color:White;height:4px;font-weight:bold">Forecasting <br />Legends</td>

</tr>
<tr style="height:70px;padding-top:20px">
<td valign="top" align="center" style="padding-top:10px">

</tr>
</tr>

```

```

        <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
            <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-
Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Reliable stocks,India</td>
        </tr>
        <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:10px">
            <td valign="top" align="center"
style="padding-top:10px">
                
            </tr>
            <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
                <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-
Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Xanther stocks,USA</td>
            </tr>
            <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:20px">
                <td valign="top" align="center"
style="padding-top:10px">
                    
                </tr>
                <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
                    <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-
Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Monger stocks talks, UK</td>
                </tr>
            </table>
        </td>
        <td valign="top" class="style1">
            <table align="left" border="2" style="border-
color:Blue" height="500px" width="100%">
                <tr style="height:5px">
                    <td width="100%" valign="top"
style="background-color:#071D7D;color:White;height:5px;font-
weight:bold">Cluster</td>
                </tr>
                <tr style="height:580px">
                    <td valign="top" align="left" style="font-
size:large; padding-left:10px;padding-right:10px;color:Black">
                        <br /><FONT style="FONT-FAMILY: Verdana;
COLOR: #993300; FONT-SIZE: 16px;font-weight:bold"> </font><BR><br />
                    </td>
                </tr>
            </table>
        </td>
    </tr>
</table>
<table border="0" cellspacing="3" cellpadding="3" align="center" width="100%"
style="vertical-align:right ">
<tr align="left">
<center>Cluster Name:IT</center>
<td class="style2" align="center" >

<asp:DataGrid runat="server" ID="dgIT">
<HeaderStyle BackColor="DarkOliveGreen" Font-Bold="true" ForeColor="White" />
<ItemStyle Font-Size="15px" />
<AlternatingItemStyle BackColor="AliceBlue" />
</asp:DataGrid></td>

```

```

        </tr>
        <tr align="left">

<td class="style2" align="center" >

<center>Cluster Name:Bank</center>
<asp:DataGrid runat="server" ID="dgbank">
<HeaderStyle BackColor="DarkOliveGreen" Font-Bold="true" ForeColor="White" />
<ItemStyle Font-Size="15px" />
<AlternatingItemStyle BackColor="AliceBlue" />
</asp:DataGrid></td>

        </tr>
        <tr align="left">

<td class="style2" align="center" >

<center>Cluster Name:Parma</center>
<asp:DataGrid runat="server" ID="dgparma">
<HeaderStyle BackColor="DarkOliveGreen" Font-Bold="true" ForeColor="White" />
<ItemStyle Font-Size="15px" />
<AlternatingItemStyle BackColor="AliceBlue" />
</asp:DataGrid></td>

        </tr>
    </table>
</td>
    </table>

        </div>

    </td>

</tr>
</table>

        </td>
    </tr>
</table>
</td>

        <!--<td valign="top" width="20%">
            <table align="left" border="2" style="border-color:Blue"
height="300px" width="100%">
                <tr><td valign="top" width="25%">
                    <table border="0" cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0">

                        <tr style="height:6px">
                            <td width="100%" style="background-
color:#071D7D;color:White;height:4px;font-weight:bold">Forecasting          <br
/>Legends</td>

```

```

        </tr>
        <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:20px">
            <td valign="top" align="center"
style="padding-top:10px">
                
            </tr>
            <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
                <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-
Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Reliable stocks,India</td>
            </tr>
            <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:10px">
                <td valign="top" align="center"
style="padding-top:10px">
                
            </tr>
            <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
                <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-
Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Xanther stocks,USA</td>
            </tr>
            <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:20px">
                <td valign="top" align="center"
style="padding-top:10px">
                
            </tr>
            <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
                <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-
Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Monger stocks talks, UK</td>
            </tr>
        </table>
    </td></tr></table>
</td></tr></table></td>

        </tr>
    </table>
</td>
</tr>
</table></div>
<!--<table align="left" border="1">
<tr align="left">
<td align="left">
<script type="text/javascript">

/*****
* Carousel Slideshow script- © Ger Versluis 2003

```

```

* Permission granted to DynamicDrive.com to feature script
* This notice must stay intact for legal use
* Visit http://www.dynamicdrive.com/ for full source code
*****/

/*****
Create a div with transparent place holder in your html
<div id="Carousel" style="position:relative">
    
</div>
placeholder width:
    4 sided: 1.42 * carousel image width + 3
    6 sided: 2 * carousel image width +4
    8 sided: 2.62 * carousel image width + 5
    12 sided: 3.87 * carousel image width + 7
placeholder height:
    carousel image height+2

Insert onload in body tag
    <body onload="Carousel()">
*****/

// 7 variables to control behavior
var Car_Image_Width=402;
var Car_Image_Height=202;
var Car_Border=true;           // true or false
var Car_Border_Color="white";
var Car_Speed=4;
var Car_Direction=true;       // true or false
var Car_NoOfSides=8;          // must be 4, 6, 8 or 12

/* array to specify images and optional links.
For 4 sided carousel specify at least 2 images
For 6 sided carousel specify at least 3
For 8 sided carousel specify at least 4
For 12 sided carousel specify at least 6
If Link is not needed keep it ""
*/
Car_Image_Sources=new Array(
    "images/a.jpg","",
    "images/b.jpg","",
    "images/c.jpg","", //this slide isn't linked
    "images/d.jpg","", // NOTE No comma after last line
);

/***** DO NOT EDIT BELOW *****/
CW_I=new Array(Car_NoOfSides/2+1);C_ClcW=new Array(Car_NoOfSides/2);
C_Coef=new Array(
    3*Math.PI/2,0,3*Math.PI/2,11*Math.PI/6,Math.PI/6,3*Math.PI/2,7*Math.PI/
4, 0,
    Math.PI/4,3*Math.PI/2,5*Math.PI/3,11*Math.PI/6,0,Math.PI/6,Math.PI/3);
var
C_CoefOf=Car_NoOfSides==4?0:Car_NoOfSides==6?2:Car_NoOfSides==8?5:9;
C_Pre_Img=new Array(Car_Image_Sources.length);

```

```

var
C_Angle=Car_Direction*Math.PI/(Car_NoOfSides/2):0,C_CrImg=Car_NoOfSides,C_Max
W,C_TotalW,
  C_Stppd=false,i,C_LeftOffset,C_HalfNo=Car_NoOfSides/2;

function Carousel(){
  if(document.getElementById){
    for(i=0;i<Car_Image_Sources.length;i+=2){
      C_Pre_Img[i]=new
Image();C_Pre_Img[i].src=Car_Image_Sources[i]}

  C_MaxW=Car_Image_Width/Math.sin(Math.PI/Car_NoOfSides)+C_HalfNo+1;
  Car_Div=document.getElementById("Carousel");
  for(i=0;i<C_HalfNo;i++){

CW_I[i]=document.createElement("img");Car_Div.appendChild(CW_I[i]);
  CW_I[i].style.position="absolute";
  CW_I[i].style.top=0+"px";
  CW_I[i].style.height=Car_Image_Height+"px";
  if(Car_Border){
    CW_I[i].style.borderStyle="solid";
    CW_I[i].style.borderWidth=1+"px";
    CW_I[i].style.borderColor=Car_Border_Color}
  CW_I[i].src=Car_Image_Sources[2*i];
  CW_I[i].lnk=Car_Image_Sources[2*i+1];
  CW_I[i].onclick=C_LdLnk;
  CW_I[i].onmouseover=C_Stp;
  CW_I[i].onmouseout=C_Rstrt}
  CarImages()}}

function CarImages(){
  if(!C_Stppd){
    C_TotalW=0;
    for(i=0;i<C_HalfNo;i++){

  C_ClcW[i]=Math.round(Math.cos(Math.abs(C_Coef[C_CoefOf+i]+C_Angle))*Car
_Image_Width);

    C_TotalW+=C_ClcW[i]}
  C_LeftOffset=(C_MaxW-C_TotalW)/2;
  for(i=0;i<C_HalfNo;i++){
    CW_I[i].style.left=C_LeftOffset+"px";
    CW_I[i].style.width=C_ClcW[i]+"px";
    C_LeftOffset+=C_ClcW[i]}
  C_Angle+=Car_Speed/720*Math.PI*(Car_Direction?-1:1);

  if((Car_Direction&&C_Angle<=0)||(!Car_Direction&&C_Angle>=Math.PI/C_Hal
fNo)){
    if(C_CrImg==Car_Image_Sources.length)C_CrImg=0;
    if(Car_Direction){
      CW_I[C_HalfNo]=CW_I[0];
      for(i=0;i<C_HalfNo;i++)CW_I[i]=CW_I[i+1];
      CW_I[C_HalfNo-
1].src=Car_Image_Sources[C_CrImg];
      CW_I[C_HalfNo-
1].lnk=Car_Image_Sources[C_CrImg+1]}
    else{ for(i=C_HalfNo;i>0;i--)CW_I[i]=CW_I[i-1];
      CW_I[0]=CW_I[C_HalfNo];

```

```

                CW_I[0].src=Car_Image_Sources[C_CrImg];
                CW_I[0].lnk=Car_Image_Sources[C_CrImg+1]}
                C_Angle=Car_Direction?Math.PI/C_HalfNo:0;C_CrImg+=2}}
                setTimeout("CarImages()",50)}

        function C_LdLnk(){if(this.lnk>window.location.href=this.lnk)
        function
C_Stp(){this.style.cursor=this.lnk?"pointer":"default";C_Stppd=true;}
        function C_Rstrt(){C_Stppd=false}
</script>
</td></tr></table>

        <table border="1"><tr><td><div id="Carousel" style="position:relative">

</div></td></tr></table>-->
        <%--<div>
        <div id="carousel">
        <div><a href="#"></a></div>

        <div><a href="#"></a></div>

        <div><a href="#"></a></div>

        <div><a href="#"></a></div>

        <div><a href="#"></a></div>

        <div><a href="#"></a></div>
</div>--%>
        </div>
        </form>
</body>
</html>

```

Server side:

```

using System;
using System.Collections;
using System.Configuration;
using System.Data;
using System.Linq;
using System.Web;
using System.Web.Security;
using System.Web.UI;
using System.Web.UI.HtmlControls;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls.WebParts;
using System.Xml.Linq;
using System.Data.SqlClient;

public partial class Cluster : System.Web.UI.Page

```

```

{
    protected void Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        SqlConnection con = new
SqlConnection("Server=Personalpc;Database=suresh;Trusted_Connection=True");
        try
        {
            con.Open();
            String Squery = "select companyname as 'Company Name',cvalue as
'Current Value',pvalue as 'Change' from cshare where type='IT' ";
            SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand(Squery, con);
            SqlDataAdapter Da = new SqlDataAdapter(Squery, con);
            DataSet ds = new DataSet();
            Da.Fill(ds);

            // gvDisplay.DataSource = ds;
            //gvDisplay.DataBind();

            //dtDisplay.DataSource = ds;
            //dtDisplay.DataBind();

            dgIT.DataSource = ds;
            dgIT.DataBind();

            String Squery1 = "select companyname as 'Company Name',cvalue as
'Current Value',pvalue as 'Change' from cshare where type='Bank' ";
            SqlCommand cmd1 = new SqlCommand(Squery1, con);
            SqlDataAdapter Da1 = new SqlDataAdapter(Squery1, con);
            DataSet ds1 = new DataSet();
            Da1.Fill(ds1);

            // gvDisplay.DataSource = ds;
            //gvDisplay.DataBind();

            //dtDisplay.DataSource = ds;
            //dtDisplay.DataBind();

            dgbank.DataSource = ds1;
            dgbank.DataBind();

            String Squery2 = "select companyname as 'Company Name' ,cvalue as
'Current Value',pvalue as 'Change' from cshare where type='Para' ";
            SqlCommand cmd2 = new SqlCommand(Squery2, con);
            SqlDataAdapter Da2 = new SqlDataAdapter(Squery2, con);
            DataSet ds2 = new DataSet();
            Da2.Fill(ds2);

            // gvDisplay.DataSource = ds;
            //gvDisplay.DataBind();

            //dtDisplay.DataSource = ds;
            //dtDisplay.DataBind();

            dgparma.DataSource = ds2;
            dgparma.DataBind();
        }
    }
}

```

```

        catch (Exception es)
        {
            Response.Write(es.Message);
        }
    }
}

```

Dataset.aspx

Client side:

```

<%@ Page Language="C#" AutoEventWireup="true" CodeFile="Dataset.aspx.cs"
Inherits="AcceptedPapers" %>

<!DOCTYPE html PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD XHTML 1.0 Transitional//EN"
"http://www.w3.org/TR/xhtml1/DTD/xhtml1-transitional.dtd">

<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml" >
<head id="Head1" runat="server">
    <title>Welcome!</title>
    <!-- slideshow---***** 3d*****-->
    <script type="text/javascript" language="javascript">
        function Check()
        {
            if(document.getElementById("txtUserName").value == "")
            {
                alert("Please Enter AccountNo.");
                return false;
            }

            if(document.getElementById("txtPassword").value == "")
            {
                alert("Please Enter Mobile No.");
                return false;
            }

            if(document.getElementById("txtUserName").value == "admin" &&
document.getElementById("txtPassword").value == "admin")
            {
                location.href="Billing.aspx";
            }
            else
            {
                alert("Please enter correct username and password");
            }
        }
    </script>

```

```

    }

    return true;

    alert("Amount Payed Successfully");
    location.href="Billing.aspx";

    return true;

}
</script>
<style type="text/css">
#carousel{

    width:900px;
    height:200px;
    position:relative;
    border:0px ;
}

/*img{
    width:100%;
    height:100%;
    border:0px ;
}*/

</style>
<script src="menu/mootools.js" type="text/javascript"></script>

<script src="menu/3dcarousel.js" type="text/javascript"></script>

<style type="text/css">

/*Credits: By Santosh Setty (http://webdesigninfo.wordpress.com) */
/*Posted to: Dynamic Drive CSS Library (http://www.dynamicdrive.com/style/)
*/

.glossymenu{
    position: relative;
    padding: 0 0 0 10px;
    margin: 0 auto 0 auto;
    background: url(menu/menub_bg.gif) repeat-x; /*tab background image
path*/
    height: 46px;
    list-style: none;
}

.glossymenu li{
    float:left;
}

.glossymenu li a{
    float: left;
    display: block;

```

```

        color:#000;
        text-decoration: none;
        font-family: sans-serif;
        font-size: 15px;
        font-weight: bold;
        padding:0 0 0 18px; /*Padding to accomodate left tab image. Do not
change*/
        height: 46px;
        line-height: 46px;
        text-align: center;
        cursor: pointer;
    }

.glossymenu li a b{
    float: left;
    display: block;
    padding: 0 20px 0 20px; /*Padding of menu items*/
}

.glossymenu li.current a, .glossymenu li a:hover{
    color: #fff;
    background: url(menu/menub_hover_left.gif) no-repeat; /*left tab image
path*/
    background-position: left;
}

.glossymenu li.current a b, .glossymenu li a:hover b{
    color: #fff;
    background: url(menu/menub_hover_right.gif) no-repeat right top;
/*right tab image path*/
}

</style>
<script type="text/javascript" language="JavaScript1.1">
<!--

/*
JavaScript Image slideshow:
By (www.wsabstract.com)
Over 200+ free JavaScript here!
*/

var slideimages=new Array()
var slidelinks=new Array()
function slideshowimages(){
for (i=0;i<slideshowimages.arguments.length;i++){
slideimages[i]=new Image()
slideimages[i].src=slideshowimages.arguments[i]
}
}

function slideshowlinks(){
for (i=0;i<slideshowlinks.arguments.length;i++)
slidelinks[i]=slideshowlinks.arguments[i]
}

```

```

function gotoshow(){
if (!window.winslide||winslide.closed)
winslide=window.open(slidelinks[whichlink])
else
winslide.location=slidelinks[whichlink]
winslide.focus()
}

//-->
</script>
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=iso-8859-1"
/>

<meta name="description" content="2011 International Conference on Computing
and Computer Vision" />

<meta content="Ziad Kobti" name="Author" />

<meta http-equiv="Content-Style-Type" content="text/css" />
<meta content="MSHTML 6.00.6000.16735" name="GENERATOR" />

<meta http-equiv="content-type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
<meta http-equiv="imagetoolbar" content="no" />
<meta name="keywords" content="slideman, sliderman.js, javascript
slider, jquery, slideshow, effects" />
<meta name="description" content="Sliderman.js - will do all the
sliding for you :)" />
<style type="text/css">
* { margin: 0; outline: none; }
body { background-color: #444444; }
.c { clear: both; }
#wrapper { margin: 0 auto; width: 560px; }
h2 { font-size: 24px; line-height: 40px; font-weight: normal;
color: #adc276; text-shadow: 0 1px 3px #222222; }
</style>
<style type="text/css">

/*Credits: Dynamic Drive CSS Library */
/*URL: http://www.dynamicdrive.com/style/ */

.sidebarmenu ul{
margin: 0;
padding: 0;
list-style-type: none;
font: bold 13px Verdana;
width: 170px; /* Main Menu Item widths */
border-bottom: 1px solid #ccc;
}

.sidebarmenu ul li{
position: relative;
}

/* Top level menu links style */
.sidebarmenu ul li a{
display: block;

```

```

overflow: auto; /*force hasLayout in IE7 */
color: white;
text-decoration: none;
padding: 6px;
border-bottom: 1px solid #778;
border-right: 1px solid #778;
}

.sidebarmenu ul li a:link, .sidebarmenu ul li a:visited, .sidebarmenu ul li
a:active{
background-color:#071D7D; /*background of tabs (default state)*/
}

.sidebarmenu ul li a:visited{
color: white;
}

.sidebarmenu ul li a:hover{
background-color: black;
}

/*Sub level menu items */
.sidebarmenu ul li ul{
position: absolute;
width: 170px; /*Sub Menu Items width */
top: 0;
visibility: hidden;
}

.sidebarmenu a.subfolderstyle{
background: url(right.gif) no-repeat 97% 50%;
}

/* Holly Hack for IE */
* html .sidebarmenu ul li { float: left; height: 1%; }
* html .sidebarmenu ul li a { height: 1%; }
/* End */
<style type="text/css">

/*Credits: Dynamic Drive CSS Library */
/*URL: http://www.dynamicdrive.com/style/ */

#dblueblockmenu{
border: 1px solid black;
border-bottom-width: 0;
width: 185px;
}

#dblueblockmenu ul{
margin: 0;
padding: 0;
list-style-type: none;
font: normal 90% 'Trebuchet MS', 'Lucida Grande', Arial, sans-serif;
}

#dblueblockmenu li a{

```

```

display: block;
padding: 3px 0;
padding-left: 0px;
width: 169px; /*185px minus all left/right paddings and margins*/
text-decoration: none;
color: white;
background-color: #2175bc;
border-bottom: 1px solid #90bade;
border-left: 7px solid #1958b7;
}

* html #ddblueblockmenu li a{ /*IE only */
width: 187px; /*IE 5*/
width: 169px; /*185px minus all left/right paddings and margins*/
}

#ddblueblockmenu li a:hover {
background-color: #2586d7;
border-left-color: #1c64d1;
}

#ddblueblockmenu div.menutitle{
color: white;
border-bottom: 1px solid black;
padding: 1px 0;
padding-left: 0px;
background-color: black;
font: bold 90% 'Trebuchet MS', 'Lucida Grande', Arial, sans-serif;
}

</style>

<script type="text/javascript">

//Nested Side Bar Menu (Mar 20th, 09)
//By Dynamic Drive: http://www.dynamicdrive.com/style/

var menuids=["sidebarmenu1"] //Enter id(s) of each Side Bar Menu's main UL,
separated by commas

function initsidebarmenu(){
for (var i=0; i<menuids.length; i++){
var ultags=document.getElementById(menuids[i]).getElementsByTagName("ul")
for (var t=0; t<ultags.length; t++){
ultags[t].parentNode.getElementsByTagName("a")[0].className+="
subfolderstyle"
if (ultags[t].parentNode.parentNode.id==menuids[i]) //if this is a first
level submenu
ultags[t].style.left=ultags[t].parentNode.offsetWidth+"px" //dynamically
position first level submenus to be width of main menu item
else //else if this is a sub level submenu (ul)
ultags[t].style.left=ultags[t-
1].getElementsByTagName("a")[0].offsetWidth+"px" //position menu to the right
of menu item that activated it
}
}
}

```

```

    ultags[t].parentNode.onmouseover=function(){
    this.getElementsByTagName("ul")[0].style.display="block"
    }
    ultags[t].parentNode.onmouseout=function(){
    this.getElementsByTagName("ul")[0].style.display="none"
    }
    }
    for (var t=ultags.length-1; t>-1; t--){ //loop through all sub menus again,
and use "display:none" to hide menus (to prevent possible page scrollbars
    ultags[t].style.visibility="visible"
    ultags[t].style.display="none"
    }
    }
}

if (window.addEventListener)
window.addEventListener("load", initsidebarmenu, false)
else if (window.attachEvent)
window.attachEvent("onload", initsidebarmenu)

</script>

```

```

<!-- sliderman.js -->
<script type="text/javascript" src="img/sliderman.1.2.1.js"></script>
<link rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" href="img/sliderman.css" />
<!-- /sliderman.js -->

```

```

<style type="text/css">.A {

    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; FONT-SIZE: 11px; FONT-FAMILY: Verdana,Arial; TEXT-
ALIGN: left; TEXT-DECORATION: none

}

.A:link {

    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #808080; TEXT-DECORATION: none

}

.A:visited {

    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #808080; TEXT-DECORATION: none

}

.A:hover {

    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #000080

}

.A:active {

```

```
        FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #000080
    }
    .B {
        FONT-WEIGHT: bold; FONT-SIZE: 11px; FONT-FAMILY: Verdana,Arial; TEXT-
        ALIGN: left; TEXT-DECORATION: none
    }
    .B:link {
        FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #ffffcc; TEXT-DECORATION: none
    }
    .B:visited {
        FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #ffffcc; TEXT-DECORATION: none
    }
    .B:hover {
        FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: Black
    }
    .B:active {
        FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #000080
    }

    .style1
    {
        width: 602px;
    }

    .style2
    {
        width: 171px;
    }
    .style3
    {
        width: 134px;
    }

</style>

<!--
text-align:center
font-style:oblique
font-size:16;
word-spacing:3em;letter-spacing:1em;text-transform:uppercase;vertical-
align:super;line-height:120%
```

-->

</head>

```
<body style="background-color:White" onload="Carousel()">
  <form id="form1" runat="server">
```

```
    <div>
```

```
      <table border="0" cellpadding="0" width="100%" cellspacing="0">
        <tr>
```

```

          <td style="background-color:#071D7D;
color:White; size:50%">
```

Forecast

```

          <td style="background-color:#071D7D;
color:White; size:50%">
            <h1/><center /><strong />Time Series
          </td>
```

```

          <td style="background-color:#071D7D;
size:5%">
```

```

            <!---->
```

```

            <table align="right"><tr ><td
valign="top">
```

```

              <a
href="javascript:gotoshow()"></a>
```

```
</script>
```

```
<!--
```

```
//configure the paths of the images, plus corresponding target links
slideshowimages("images/pic1.jpg","images/pic2.jpg","images/pic3.jpg")
//slideshowlinks("http://food.epicurious.com/run/recipe/view?id=13285","http:
//food.epicurious.com/run/recipe/view?id=10092","http://food.epicurious.com/r
un/recipe/view?id=100975","http://food.epicurious.com/run/recipe/view?id=2876
","http://food.epicurious.com/run/recipe/view?id=20010")
```

```
//configure the speed of the slideshow, in miliseconds
var slideshowspeed=4000
```

```
var whichlink=0
var whichimage=0
```

```

function slideit(){
if (!document.images)
return
document.images.slide.src=slideimages[whichimage].src
whichlink=whichimage
if (whichimage<slideimages.length-1)
whichimage++
else
whichimage=0
setTimeout("slideit()",slideshowspeed)
}
slideit()

//-->
</script>
</table>

</td>
</tr>
</table>
</td>
</tr>

</table>

</td>
</tr>
<tr valign="top">
<td colspan="3" valign="top"><div>
<ul class="glossymenu" style="width=100%">
<li><a href="Home.aspx"><b>Home</b></a></li>
<li class="current"><a href="Dataset.aspx"><b>Dataset</b></a></li>
<li><a href="Index.aspx"><b>Index</b></a></li>
<li><a href="Cluster.aspx"><b>Cluster</b></a></li>
<li><a href="Weight.aspx"><b>Weight</b></a></li>
<li><a href="Forecast.aspx"><b>Forecast</b></a></li>
</ul></div></td>
</tr>
<tr valign="top">
<td valign="top"><table cellpadding="0" style="vertical-align:top" cellspacing="5" border="0" ><tr valign="top">
<td valign="top" width="12%">

<table border="2" style="border-color:Blue">
<tr style="height:6px">
<td width="100%" style="background-color:#071D7D;color:White;height:4px;font-weight:bold">Forecasting <br />Legends</td>

</tr>
<tr style="height:70px;padding-top:20px">
<td valign="top" align="center" style="padding-top:10px">

</tr>
</tr>

```

```

        <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
            <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-
Relief;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Reliable stocks,India</td>
        </tr>
        <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:10px">
            <td valign="top" align="center"
style="padding-top:10px">
                
            </tr>
            <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
                <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-
Relief;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Xanther stocks,USA</td>
            </tr>
            <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:20px">
                <td valign="top" align="center"
style="padding-top:10px">
                    
                </tr>
            <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
                <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-
Relief;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Monger stocks talks, UK</td>
            </tr>
        </table>
    </td>
        <td valign="top" class="style1">
            <table align="left" border="2" style="border-
color:Blue" height="500px" width="100%">
                <tr style="height:5px">
                    <td width="100%" valign="top"
style="background-color:#071D7D;color:White;height:5px;font-
weight:bold">Company Registration</td>
                </tr>
                <tr style="height:580px">
                    <td valign="top" align="left" style="font-
size:large; padding-left:10px;padding-right:10px;color:Black">
                        <br /><FONT style="FONT-FAMILY: Verdana;
COLOR: #993300; FONT-SIZE: 16px;font-weight:bold"> Welcome! Register Your
Company</font><BR>
                            <asp:Label ID="Lb11" runat="server"
></asp:Label>
                                <br />
                    </td>
                </tr>
            </table>
        </td>
    </tr>
</table>
<table border="0" cellspacing="3" cellpadding="3" align="center" width="100%"
style="vertical-align:right ">
<tr align="left">
<td class="style2" ></td>
<td align="right" style="padding-left:10px" class="style3">
    <b>Type</b>
</td>
</tr>
</table>

```

```

        <asp:DropDownList runat="server" ID="ddl1"><asp:ListItem Text="IT"
Value="IT" ></asp:ListItem><asp:ListItem Text="Bank" Value="Bank"
></asp:ListItem><asp:ListItem Text="Parma" Value="Parma">
    </asp:ListItem></asp:DropDownList>
    </td>
</tr>
<tr align="left">
<td class="style2"></td> <td align="right" class="style3">
    <b>Company Name</b>
    </td>
    <td>
<asp:TextBox ID="txtUserName" runat="server"></asp:TextBox>
    </td>
</tr>

<tr><td class="style2"></td>
<td align="right" style="padding-left:10px" class="style3">
    <b>Current</b>
    </td>
    <td>
<asp:TextBox ID="txtcurrent" runat="server"></asp:TextBox>
    </td>
</tr>
<tr><td class="style2"></td>
<td align="right" style="padding-left:10px" class="style3">
    <b>Change</b>
    </td>
    <td>
<asp:TextBox ID="txtchange" runat="server"></asp:TextBox>
    </td>
</tr>
<tr><td class="style2"></td>
<td align="right" style="padding-left:10px" class="style3">
    <b>Change Percentage</b>
    </td>
    <td>
<asp:TextBox ID="txtCPercentage" runat="server"></asp:TextBox>
    </td>
</tr>
<tr><td class="style2"></td>
<td align="right" style="padding-left:10px" class="style3">
    <b>Open</b>
    </td>
    <td>
<asp:TextBox ID="txtOpen" runat="server"></asp:TextBox>
    </td>
</tr>
<tr><td class="style2"></td>
<td align="right" style="padding-left:10px" class="style3">
    <b>High</b>
    </td>
    <td>
<asp:TextBox ID="txtHigh" runat="server"></asp:TextBox>
    </td>
</tr>
<tr><td class="style2"></td>
<td align="right" style="padding-left:10px" class="style3">

```



```

                <td width="100%" style="background-
color:#071D7D;color:White;height:4px;font-weight:bold">Forecasting <br
/>Legends</td>

            </tr>
            <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:20px">
                <td valign="top" align="center"
style="padding-top:10px">
                    
                </tr>
                <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
                    <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-
Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Reliable stocks,India</td>
                </tr>
                <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:10px">
                    <td valign="top" align="center"
style="padding-top:10px">
                        
                    </tr>
                    <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
                        <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-
Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Xanther stocks,USA</td>
                    </tr>
                    <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:20px">
                        <td valign="top" align="center"
style="padding-top:10px">
                            
                        </tr>
                        <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
                            <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-
Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Monger stocks talks, UK</td>
                        </tr>
                    </table>
                </td></tr></table>

</td><!--%>

</tr></table></td>

        </tr>

    </table>
    </td>
</tr>
</table></div>
<!--<table align="left" border="1">
<tr align="left">
<td align="left">
<script type="text/javascript">

```

```

/*****
* Carousel Slideshow script- © Ger Versluis 2003
* Permission granted to DynamicDrive.com to feature script
* This notice must stay intact for legal use
* Visit http://www.dynamicdrive.com/ for full source code
*****/

/*****
Create a div with transparent place holder in your html
<div id="Carousel" style="position:relative">
    
</div>
placeholder width:
    4 sided: 1.42 * carousel image width + 3
    6 sided: 2 * carousel image width +4
    8 sided: 2.62 * carousel image width + 5
    12 sided: 3.87 * carousel image width + 7
placeholder height:
    carousel image height+2

Insert onload in body tag
    <body onload="Carousel()">
*****/

// 7 variables to control behavior
var Car_Image_Width=402;
var Car_Image_Height=202;
var Car_Border=true;           // true or false
var Car_Border_Color="white";
var Car_Speed=4;
var Car_Direction=true;       // true or false
var Car_NoOfSides=8;          // must be 4, 6, 8 or 12

/* array to specify images and optional links.
For 4 sided carousel specify at least 2 images
For 6 sided carousel specify at least 3
For 8 sided carousel specify at least 4
For 12 sided carousel specify at least 6
If Link is not needed keep it ""
*/
Car_Image_Sources=new Array(
    "images/a.jpg","",
    "images/b.jpg","",
    "images/c.jpg","", //this slide isn't linked
    "images/d.jpg","", // NOTE No comma after last line
);

/***** DO NOT EDIT BELOW *****/
CW_I=new Array(Car_NoOfSides/2+1);C_ClcW=new Array(Car_NoOfSides/2);
C_Coef=new Array(
    3*Math.PI/2,0,3*Math.PI/2,11*Math.PI/6,Math.PI/6,3*Math.PI/2,7*Math.PI/
4, 0,
    Math.PI/4,3*Math.PI/2,5*Math.PI/3,11*Math.PI/6,0,Math.PI/6,Math.PI/3);

```

```

var
C_CoefOf=Car_NoOfSides==4?0:Car_NoOfSides==6?2:Car_NoOfSides==8?5:9;
C_Pre_Img=new Array(Car_Image_Sources.length);
var
C_Angle=Car_Direction?Math.PI/(Car_NoOfSides/2):0,C_CrImg=Car_NoOfSides,C_Max
W,C_TotalW,
C_Stppd=false,i,C_LeftOffset,C_HalfNo=Car_NoOfSides/2;

function Carousel(){
if(document.getElementById){
for(i=0;i<Car_Image_Sources.length;i+=2){
C_Pre_Img[i]=new
Image();C_Pre_Img[i].src=Car_Image_Sources[i]}

C_MaxW=Car_Image_Width/Math.sin(Math.PI/Car_NoOfSides)+C_HalfNo+1;
Car_Div=document.getElementById("Carousel");
for(i=0;i<C_HalfNo;i++){

CW_I[i]=document.createElement("img");Car_Div.appendChild(CW_I[i]);
CW_I[i].style.position="absolute";
CW_I[i].style.top=0+"px";
CW_I[i].style.height=Car_Image_Height+"px";
if(Car_Border){
CW_I[i].style.borderStyle="solid";
CW_I[i].style.borderWidth=1+"px";
CW_I[i].style.borderColor=Car_Border_Color}
CW_I[i].src=Car_Image_Sources[2*i];
CW_I[i].lnk=Car_Image_Sources[2*i+1];
CW_I[i].onclick=C_LdLnk;
CW_I[i].onmouseover=C_Stp;
CW_I[i].onmouseout=C_Rstrt}
CarImages()}}

function CarImages(){
if(!C_Stppd){
C_TotalW=0;
for(i=0;i<C_HalfNo;i++){

C_ClcW[i]=Math.round(Math.cos(Math.abs(C_Coef[C_CoefOf+i]+C_Angle))*Car
_Image_Width);

C_TotalW+=C_ClcW[i]}
C_LeftOffset=(C_MaxW-C_TotalW)/2;
for(i=0;i<C_HalfNo;i++){
CW_I[i].style.left=C_LeftOffset+"px";
CW_I[i].style.width=C_ClcW[i]+"px";
C_LeftOffset+=C_ClcW[i]}
C_Angle+=Car_Speed/720*Math.PI*(Car_Direction?-1:1);

if((Car_Direction&&C_Angle<=0)||(!Car_Direction&&C_Angle>=Math.PI/C_Hal
fNo))){
if(C_CrImg==Car_Image_Sources.length)C_CrImg=0;
if(Car_Direction){
CW_I[C_HalfNo]=CW_I[0];
for(i=0;i<C_HalfNo;i++)CW_I[i]=CW_I[i+1];
CW_I[C_HalfNo-
1].src=Car_Image_Sources[C_CrImg];

```

```

        CW_I[C_HalfNo-
1].lnk=Car_Image_Sources[C_CrImg+1]}
        else{ for(i=C_HalfNo;i>0;i--)CW_I[i]=CW_I[i-1];
        CW_I[0]=CW_I[C_HalfNo];
        CW_I[0].src=Car_Image_Sources[C_CrImg];
        CW_I[0].lnk=Car_Image_Sources[C_CrImg+1]}
        C_Angle=Car_Direction?Math.PI/C_HalfNo:0;C_CrImg+=2}}
        setTimeout("CarImages()",50)}

        function C_LdLnk(){if(this.lnk>window.location.href=this.lnk)
        function
C_Stp(){this.style.cursor=this.lnk?"pointer":"default";C_Stppd=true;}
        function C_Rstrt(){C_Stppd=false}
</script>
</td></tr></table>

        <table border="1"><tr><td><div id="Carousel" style="position:relative">

</div></td></tr></table>-->
        <%--<div>
        <div id="carousel">
        <div><a href="#"></a></div>

        <div><a href="#"></a></div>

        <div><a href="#"></a></div>

        <div><a href="#"></a></div>

        <div><a href="#"></a></div>

        <div><a href="#"></a></div>
</div>--%>
        </div>
        </form>
</body>
</html>

```

Server side:

```

using System;
using System.Data;
using System.Configuration;
using System.Collections;
using System.Web;
using System.Web.Security;
using System.Web.UI;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls.WebParts;
using System.Web.UI.HtmlControls;
using System.Data.SqlClient;

```

```

public partial class AcceptedPapers : System.Web.UI.Page
{
    protected void Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        SqlConnection con = new
SqlConnection("Server=Personalpc;Database=suresh;Trusted_Connection=True");
        try
        {
            con.Open();
            String Squery = "insert into
cshare([type],[companyname],[cvalue],[pvalue],[per],[sopen],[shigh],[slow],[v
olume],[code]) values('" + ddl1.Selected.Value + "','" + txtUserName.Text +
 "','" + txtcurrent.Text+ "','"+ txtchange.Text+ "','"+
txtCPercentage.Text+ "','"+txtOpen.Text+ "','"+
txtHigh.Text+ "','"+txtLow.Text+ "','"+txtVolume.Text+ "','"+ddl2.Selected.Value+
 "') ";
            SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand(Squery, con);
            cmd.ExecuteNonQuery();
            txtVolume.Text = "";
            txtUserName.Text = "";
            txtOpen.Text = "";
            txtLow.Text = "";
            txtHigh.Text = "";
            txtcurrent.Text = "";
            txtCPercentage.Text = "";
            txtchange.Text = "";
            Lbl1.Text = "Thank you for registering your company";
            con.Close();
        }
        catch (Exception ex)
        {
            Response.Write(ex.Message);
        }
        finally
        {
            con.Close();
        }
    }
}

```

Weight.aspx

Client side:

```

<%@ Page Language="C#" AutoEventWireup="true" CodeFile="Weight.aspx.cs"
Inherits="Weight" %>

<!DOCTYPE html PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD XHTML 1.0 Transitional//EN"
"http://www.w3.org/TR/xhtml1/DTD/xhtml1-transitional.dtd">
<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml">

```

```

<head id="Head1" runat="server">
  <title>Welcome!</title>
  <!-- slideshow---***** 3d*****-->
  <script type="text/javascript" language="javascript">
    function Check()
    {
      if(document.getElementById("txtUserName").value == "")
      {
        alert("Please Enter name");
        return false;
      }

      if(document.getElementById("txtPassword").value == "")
      {
        alert("Please Enter password");
        return false;
      }

      if(document.getElementById("txtUserName").value == "admin" &&
document.getElementById("txtPassword").value == "admin")
      {
        location.href="Billing.aspx";
      }
      else
      {
        alert("Please enter correct username and password");
      }

      return true;

      alert("Amount Payed Successfully");
      location.href="Billing.aspx";

      return true;

    }
  </script>
  <style type="text/css">
  #carousel{

    width:900px;
    height:200px;
    position:relative;
    border:0px ;
  }

  /*img{
    width:100%;
    height:100%;
    border:0px ;
  }*/
</style>
<script src="menu/mootools.js" type="text/javascript"></script>

```

```
<script src="menu/3dcarousel.js" type="text/javascript"></script>
```

```
<style type="text/css">
```

```
/*Credits: By Santosh Setty (http://webdesigninfo.wordpress.com) */  
/*Posted to: Dynamic Drive CSS Library (http://www.dynamicdrive.com/style/)  
*/  
  
.glossymenu{  
    position: relative;  
    padding: 0 0 0 10px;  
    margin: 0 auto 0 auto;  
    background: url(menu/menub_bg.gif) repeat-x; /*tab background image  
path*/  
    height: 46px;  
    list-style: none;  
}  
  
.glossymenu li{  
    float:left;  
}  
  
.glossymenu li a{  
    float: left;  
    display: block;  
    color:#000;  
    text-decoration: none;  
    font-family: sans-serif;  
    font-size: 15px;  
    font-weight: bold;  
    padding:0 0 0 18px; /*Padding to accomodate left tab image. Do not  
change*/  
    height: 46px;  
    line-height: 46px;  
    text-align: center;  
    cursor: pointer;  
}  
  
.glossymenu li a b{  
    float: left;  
    display: block;  
    padding: 0 20px 0 20px; /*Padding of menu items*/  
}  
  
.glossymenu li.current a, .glossymenu li a:hover{  
    color: #fff;  
    background: url(menu/menub_hover_left.gif) no-repeat; /*left tab image  
path*/  
    background-position: left;  
}  
  
.glossymenu li.current a b, .glossymenu li a:hover b{  
    color: #fff;  
    background: url(menu/menub_hover_right.gif) no-repeat right top;  
/*right tab image path*/
```

```

}

</style>
  <script type="text/javascript" language="JavaScript1.1">
<!--

/*
JavaScript Image slideshow:
By (www.wsabstract.com)
Over 200+ free JavaScript here!
*/

var slideimages=new Array()
var slidelinks=new Array()
function slideshowimages(){
for (i=0;i<slideshowimages.arguments.length;i++){
slideimages[i]=new Image()
slideimages[i].src=slideshowimages.arguments[i]
}
}

function slideshowlinks(){
for (i=0;i<slideshowlinks.arguments.length;i++)
slidelinks[i]=slideshowlinks.arguments[i]
}

function gotoshow(){
if (!window.winslide||winslide.closed)
winslide=window.open(slidelinks[whichlink])
else
winslide.location=slidelinks[whichlink]
winslide.focus()
}

//-->
</script>
  <meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=iso-8859-1"
/>

<meta name="description" content="2011 International Conference on Computing
and Computer Vision" />

<meta content="Ziad Kobti" name="Author" />

<meta http-equiv="Content-Style-Type" content="text/css" />
<meta content="MSHTML 6.00.6000.16735" name="GENERATOR" />

  <meta http-equiv="content-type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
  <meta http-equiv="imagetoolbar" content="no" />
  <meta name="keywords" content="slideman, sliderman.js, javascript
slider, jquery, slideshow, effects" />
  <meta name="description" content="Sliderman.js - will do all the
sliding for you :)" />
  <style type="text/css">
    * { margin: 0; outline: none; }
    body { background-color: #444444; }

```

```
        .c { clear: both; }
        #wrapper { margin: 0 auto; width: 560px; }
        h2 { font-size: 24px; line-height: 40px; font-weight: normal;
color: #adc276; text-shadow: 0 1px 3px #222222; }
</style>
<style type="text/css">
```

```
/*Credits: Dynamic Drive CSS Library */
/*URL: http://www.dynamicdrive.com/style/ */
```

```
.sidebarmenu ul{
margin: 0;
padding: 0;
list-style-type: none;
font: bold 13px Verdana;
width: 170px; /* Main Menu Item widths */
border-bottom: 1px solid #ccc;
}
```

```
.sidebarmenu ul li{
position: relative;
}
```

```
/* Top level menu links style */
.sidebarmenu ul li a{
display: block;
overflow: auto; /*force hasLayout in IE7 */
color: white;
text-decoration: none;
padding: 6px;
border-bottom: 1px solid #778;
border-right: 1px solid #778;
}
```

```
.sidebarmenu ul li a:link, .sidebarmenu ul li a:visited, .sidebarmenu ul li
a:active{
background-color:#071D7D; /*background of tabs (default state)*/
}
```

```
.sidebarmenu ul li a:visited{
color: white;
}
```

```
.sidebarmenu ul li a:hover{
background-color: black;
}
```

```
/*Sub level menu items */
.sidebarmenu ul li ul{
position: absolute;
width: 170px; /*Sub Menu Items width */
top: 0;
visibility: hidden;
}
```

```
.sidebarmenu a.subfolderstyle{
background: url(right.gif) no-repeat 97% 50%;
```

```

}

/* Holly Hack for IE */
* html .sidebarmenu ul li { float: left; height: 1%; }
* html .sidebarmenu ul li a { height: 1%; }
/* End */
<style type="text/css">

/*Credits: Dynamic Drive CSS Library */
/*URL: http://www.dynamicdrive.com/style/ */

#ddbblueblockmenu{
border: 1px solid black;
border-bottom-width: 0;
width: 185px;
}

#ddbblueblockmenu ul{
margin: 0;
padding: 0;
list-style-type: none;
font: normal 90% 'Trebuchet MS', 'Lucida Grande', Arial, sans-serif;
}

#ddbblueblockmenu li a{
display: block;
padding: 3px 0;
padding-left: 0px;
width: 169px; /*185px minus all left/right paddings and margins*/
text-decoration: none;
color: white;
background-color: #2175bc;
border-bottom: 1px solid #90bade;
border-left: 7px solid #1958b7;
}

* html #ddbblueblockmenu li a{ /*IE only */
width: 187px; /*IE 5*/
width: 169px; /*185px minus all left/right paddings and margins*/
}

#ddbblueblockmenu li a:hover {
background-color: #2586d7;
border-left-color: #1c64d1;
}

#ddbblueblockmenu div.menutitle{
color: white;
border-bottom: 1px solid black;
padding: 1px 0;
padding-left: 0px;
background-color: black;
font: bold 90% 'Trebuchet MS', 'Lucida Grande', Arial, sans-serif;
}

</style>

```

```

<script type="text/javascript">

//Nested Side Bar Menu (Mar 20th, 09)
//By Dynamic Drive: http://www.dynamicdrive.com/style/

var menuids=["sidebarmenu1"] //Enter id(s) of each Side Bar Menu's main UL,
separated by commas

function initsidebarmenu(){
for (var i=0; i<menuids.length; i++){
    var ultags=document.getElementById(menuids[i]).getElementsByTagName("ul")
    for (var t=0; t<ultags.length; t++){
        ultags[t].parentNode.getElementsByTagName("a")[0].className+="
subfolderstyle"
        if (ultags[t].parentNode.parentNode.id==menuids[i]) //if this is a first
level submenu
            ultags[t].style.left=ultags[t].parentNode.offsetWidth+"px" //dynamically
position first level submenus to be width of main menu item
        else //else if this is a sub level submenu (ul)
            ultags[t].style.left=ultags[t-
1].getElementsByTagName("a")[0].offsetWidth+"px" //position menu to the right
of menu item that activated it
            ultags[t].parentNode.onmouseover=function(){
                this.getElementsByTagName("ul")[0].style.display="block"
            }
            ultags[t].parentNode.onmouseout=function(){
                this.getElementsByTagName("ul")[0].style.display="none"
            }
            }
        for (var t=ultags.length-1; t>-1; t--){ //loop through all sub menus again,
and use "display:none" to hide menus (to prevent possible page scrollbars
            ultags[t].style.visibility="visible"
            ultags[t].style.display="none"
        }
    }
}

if (window.addEventListener)
window.addEventListener("load", initsidebarmenu, false)
else if (window.attachEvent)
window.attachEvent("onload", initsidebarmenu)

</script>

<!-- sliderman.js -->
<script type="text/javascript" src="img/sliderman.1.2.1.js"></script>
<link rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" href="img/sliderman.css" />
<!-- /sliderman.js -->

<style type="text/css">.A {

```

```
        FONT-WEIGHT: bold; FONT-SIZE: 11px; FONT-FAMILY: Verdana,Arial; TEXT-  
ALIGN: left; TEXT-DECORATION: none
```

```
}
```

```
.A:link {
```

```
        FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #808080; TEXT-DECORATION: none
```

```
}
```

```
.A:visited {
```

```
        FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #808080; TEXT-DECORATION: none
```

```
}
```

```
.A:hover {
```

```
        FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #000080
```

```
}
```

```
.A:active {
```

```
        FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #000080
```

```
}
```

```
.B {
```

```
        FONT-WEIGHT: bold; FONT-SIZE: 11px; FONT-FAMILY: Verdana,Arial; TEXT-  
ALIGN: left; TEXT-DECORATION: none
```

```
}
```

```
.B:link {
```

```
        FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #ffffcc; TEXT-DECORATION: none
```

```
}
```

```
.B:visited {
```

```
        FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #ffffcc; TEXT-DECORATION: none
```

```
}
```

```
.B:hover {
```

```
        FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: Black
```

```
}
```

```
.B:active {
```

```

        FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #000080
    }

    .style1
    {
        width: 602px;
    }

    .style2
    {
        width: 171px;
    }
    .style3
    {
        width: 134px;
    }

</style>

<!--
text-align:center
font-style:oblique
font-size:16;
word-spacing:3em;letter-spacing:1em;text-transform:uppercase;vertical-
align:super;line-height:120%
-->

</head>
<body style="background-color:White" onload="Carousel()">
    <form id="form1" runat="server">

        <div>
            <table border="0" cellpadding="0" width="100%" cellspacing="0">
                <tr>

                    <td style="background-color:#071D7D;
color:White; size:50%">

                    <td style="background-color:#071D7D;

                    <h1/><center /><strong />Time Series

                    </td>

                    <td style="background-color:#071D7D;
size:5%">

```

```

                                <!---->
                                <table align="right"><tr ><td
valign="top">
                                <a
href="javascript:gotoshow()"></a>
<script>
<!--
//configure the paths of the images, plus corresponding target links
slideshowimages("images/pic1.jpg","images/pic2.jpg","images/pic3.jpg")
//slideshowlinks("http://food.epicurious.com/run/recipe/view?id=13285","http:
//food.epicurious.com/run/recipe/view?id=10092","http://food.epicurious.com/r
un/recipe/view?id=100975","http://food.epicurious.com/run/recipe/view?id=2876
","http://food.epicurious.com/run/recipe/view?id=20010")

//configure the speed of the slideshow, in miliseconds
var slideshowspeed=4000

var whichlink=0
var whichimage=0
function slideit(){
if (!document.images)
return
document.images.slide.src=slideimages[whichimage].src
whichlink=whichimage
if (whichimage<slideimages.length-1)
whichimage++
else
whichimage=0
setTimeout("slideit()",slideshowspeed)
}
slideit()

//-->
</script>
</table>
                                </td>
                                </tr>
                                </table>
                                </td>
                                </tr>
                                </table>
                                </td>
                                </tr>
                                <tr valign="top">
                                <td colspan="3" valign="top"><div>
<ul class="glossymenu" style="width=100%">
                                <li ><a href="Home.aspx"><b>Home</b></a></li>
                                <li ><a href="Dataset.aspx"><b>Dataset</b></a></li>

```

```

        <li><a href="Index.aspx"><b>Index</b></a></li>
        <li ><a href="Cluster.aspx"><b>Cluster</b></a></li>
        <li class="current"><a href="Weight.aspx"><b>Weight</b></a></li>
        <li><a href="Forecast.aspx"><b>Forecast</b></a></li>
</ul></div></td>
    </tr>
    <tr valign="top">
        <td valign="top"><table cellpadding="0" style="vertical-align:top" cellspacing="5" border="0" ><tr valign="top">
            <td valign="top" width="12%">
                <table border="2" style="border-color:Blue"
                <tr style="height:6px">
                    <td width="100%" style="background-color:#071D7D;color:White;height:4px;font-weight:bold">Forecasting <br />Legends</td>
                </tr>
                <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:20px">
                    <td valign="top" align="center"
                    style="padding-top:10px">
                        
                </tr>
                <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
                    <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Reliable stocks,India</td>
                </tr>
                <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:10px">
                    <td valign="top" align="center"
                    style="padding-top:10px">
                        
                </tr>
                <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
                    <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Xanther stocks,USA</td>
                </tr>
                <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:20px">
                    <td valign="top" align="center"
                    style="padding-top:10px">
                        
                </tr>
                <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
                    <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Monger stocks talks, UK</td>
                </tr>
            </table>
        </td>
        <td valign="top" class="style1">
            <table align="left" border="2" style="border-color:Blue" height="500px" width="100%">

```



```

                <td width="100%" style="background-
color:#071D7D;color:White;height:4px;font-weight:bold">Forecasting <br
/>Legends</td>

            </tr>
            <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:20px">
                <td valign="top" align="center"
style="padding-top:10px">
                    
                </tr>
                <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
                    <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-
Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Reliable stocks,India</td>
                </tr>
                <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:10px">
                    <td valign="top" align="center"
style="padding-top:10px">
                        
                    </tr>
                    <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
                        <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-
Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Xanther stocks,USA</td>
                    </tr>
                    <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:20px">
                        <td valign="top" align="center"
style="padding-top:10px">
                            
                        </tr>
                        <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
                            <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-
Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Monger stocks talks, UK</td>
                        </tr>
                    </table>
                </td></tr></table>

</td>--%>

</tr></table></td>

        </tr>

    </table>
    </td>
</tr>
</table></div>
<!--<table align="left" border="1">
<tr align="left">
<td align="left">
<script type="text/javascript">

```

```

/*****
* Carousel Slideshow script- © Ger Versluis 2003
* Permission granted to DynamicDrive.com to feature script
* This notice must stay intact for legal use
* Visit http://www.dynamicdrive.com/ for full source code
*****/

/*****
Create a div with transparent place holder in your html
<div id="Carousel" style="position:relative">
    
</div>
placeholder width:
    4 sided: 1.42 * carousel image width + 3
    6 sided: 2 * carousel image width +4
    8 sided: 2.62 * carousel image width + 5
    12 sided: 3.87 * carousel image width + 7
placeholder height:
    carousel image height+2

Insert onload in body tag
    <body onload="Carousel()">
*****/

// 7 variables to control behavior
var Car_Image_Width=402;
var Car_Image_Height=202;
var Car_Border=true;           // true or false
var Car_Border_Color="white";
var Car_Speed=4;
var Car_Direction=true;       // true or false
var Car_NoOfSides=8;         // must be 4, 6, 8 or 12

/* array to specify images and optional links.
For 4 sided carousel specify at least 2 images
For 6 sided carousel specify at least 3
For 8 sided carousel specify at least 4
For 12 sided carousel specify at least 6
If Link is not needed keep it ""
*/
    Car_Image_Sources=new Array(
        "images/a.jpg","",
        "images/b.jpg","",
        "images/c.jpg","", //this slide isn't linked
        "images/d.jpg","", // NOTE No comma after last line
    );

/***** DO NOT EDIT BELOW *****/
CW_I=new Array(Car_NoOfSides/2+1);C_ClcW=new Array(Car_NoOfSides/2);
C_Coef=new Array(
    3*Math.PI/2,0,3*Math.PI/2,11*Math.PI/6,Math.PI/6,3*Math.PI/2,7*Math.PI/
4, 0,
    Math.PI/4,3*Math.PI/2,5*Math.PI/3,11*Math.PI/6,0,Math.PI/6,Math.PI/3);

```

```

var
C_CoefOf=Car_NoOfSides==4?0:Car_NoOfSides==6?2:Car_NoOfSides==8?5:9;
C_Pre_Img=new Array(Car_Image_Sources.length);
var
C_Angle=Car_Direction?Math.PI/(Car_NoOfSides/2):0,C_CrImg=Car_NoOfSides,C_Max
W,C_TotalW,
C_Stppd=false,i,C_LeftOffset,C_HalfNo=Car_NoOfSides/2;

function Carousel(){
if(document.getElementById){
for(i=0;i<Car_Image_Sources.length;i+=2){
C_Pre_Img[i]=new
Image();C_Pre_Img[i].src=Car_Image_Sources[i]}

C_MaxW=Car_Image_Width/Math.sin(Math.PI/Car_NoOfSides)+C_HalfNo+1;
Car_Div=document.getElementById("Carousel");
for(i=0;i<C_HalfNo;i++){

CW_I[i]=document.createElement("img");Car_Div.appendChild(CW_I[i]);
CW_I[i].style.position="absolute";
CW_I[i].style.top=0+"px";
CW_I[i].style.height=Car_Image_Height+"px";
if(Car_Border){
CW_I[i].style.borderStyle="solid";
CW_I[i].style.borderWidth=1+"px";
CW_I[i].style.borderColor=Car_Border_Color}
CW_I[i].src=Car_Image_Sources[2*i];
CW_I[i].lnk=Car_Image_Sources[2*i+1];
CW_I[i].onclick=C_LdLnk;
CW_I[i].onmouseover=C_Stp;
CW_I[i].onmouseout=C_Rstrt}
CarImages()}}

function CarImages(){
if(!C_Stppd){
C_TotalW=0;
for(i=0;i<C_HalfNo;i++){

C_ClcW[i]=Math.round(Math.cos(Math.abs(C_Coef[C_CoefOf+i]+C_Angle))*Car
_Image_Width);

C_TotalW+=C_ClcW[i]}
C_LeftOffset=(C_MaxW-C_TotalW)/2;
for(i=0;i<C_HalfNo;i++){
CW_I[i].style.left=C_LeftOffset+"px";
CW_I[i].style.width=C_ClcW[i]+"px";
C_LeftOffset+=C_ClcW[i]}
C_Angle+=Car_Speed/720*Math.PI*(Car_Direction?-1:1);

if((Car_Direction&&C_Angle<=0)||(!Car_Direction&&C_Angle>=Math.PI/C_Hal
fNo))){
if(C_CrImg==Car_Image_Sources.length)C_CrImg=0;
if(Car_Direction){
CW_I[C_HalfNo]=CW_I[0];
for(i=0;i<C_HalfNo;i++)CW_I[i]=CW_I[i+1];
CW_I[C_HalfNo-
1].src=Car_Image_Sources[C_CrImg];

```

```

        CW_I[C_HalfNo-
1].lnk=Car_Image_Sources[C_CrImg+1]}
        else{ for(i=C_HalfNo;i>0;i--)CW_I[i]=CW_I[i-1];
        CW_I[0]=CW_I[C_HalfNo];
        CW_I[0].src=Car_Image_Sources[C_CrImg];
        CW_I[0].lnk=Car_Image_Sources[C_CrImg+1]}
        C_Angle=Car_Direction?Math.PI/C_HalfNo:0;C_CrImg+=2}}
        setTimeout("CarImages()",50)}

        function C_LdLnk(){if(this.lnk>window.location.href=this.lnk)
        function
C_Stp(){this.style.cursor=this.lnk?"pointer":"default";C_Stppd=true;}
        function C_Rstrt(){C_Stppd=false}
</script>
</td></tr></table>

        <table border="1"><tr><td><div id="Carousel" style="position:relative">

</div></td></tr></table>-->
        <%--<div>
        <div id="carousel">
        <div><a href="#"></a></div>

        <div><a href="#"></a></div>

        <div><a href="#"></a></div>

        <div><a href="#"></a></div>

        <div><a href="#"></a></div>

        <div><a href="#"></a></div>
</div>--%>
        </div>
        </form>
</body>
</html>

```

Serverside:

```

using System;
using System.Collections;
using System.Configuration;
using System.Data;
using System.Linq;
using System.Web;
using System.Web.Security;
using System.Web.UI;
using System.Web.UI.HtmlControls;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls.WebParts;
using System.Xml.Linq;
using System.Data.SqlClient;

```

```

public partial class Weight : System.Web.UI.Page
{
    protected void Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        SqlConnection con = new
SqlConnection("Server=Personalpc;Database=suresh;Trusted_Connection=True");
        try
        {
            con.Open();
            String Sqquery = "select CompanyName as 'Company Name',cvalue as
'Total No. of Shares',pvalue as 'Cost',row_number() over (order by cvalue)
Weight from cshare ";
            SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand(Sqquery, con);
            SqlDataAdapter Da = new SqlDataAdapter(Sqquery, con);
            DataSet ds = new DataSet();
            Da.Fill(ds);

            // gvDisplay.DataSource = ds;
            //gvDisplay.DataBind();

            //dtDisplay.DataSource = ds;
            //dtDisplay.DataBind();

            dgWeight.DataSource = ds;
            dgWeight.DataBind();
        }
        catch (Exception ex)
        {
            Response.Write(ex.Message);
        }
    }
}

```

Forecast.aspx

Clientside:

```

<%@ Page Language="C#" AutoEventWireup="true" CodeFile="Forecast.aspx.cs"
Inherits="Forecast" %>

```

```

<!DOCTYPE html PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD XHTML 1.0 Transitional//EN"
"http://www.w3.org/TR/xhtml1/DTD/xhtml1-transitional.dtd">
<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml">
<head id="Head1" runat="server">
    <title>Welcome!</title>
    <!-- slideshow---***** 3d*****-->
    <script type="text/javascript" language="javascript">
        function Check()

```

```

{
  if(document.getElementById("txtUserName").value == "")
  {
    alert("Please Enter name");
    return false;
  }

  if(document.getElementById("txtPassword").value == "")
  {
    alert("Please Enter password");
    return false;
  }

  if(document.getElementById("txtUserName").value == "admin" &&
document.getElementById("txtPassword").value == "admin")
  {
    location.href="Billing.aspx";
  }
  else
  {
    alert("Please enter correct username and password");
  }

  return true;

  alert("Amount Payed Successfully");
  location.href="Billing.aspx";

  return true;

}
</script>
<style type="text/css">
#carousel{

  width:900px;
  height:200px;
  position:relative;
  border:0px ;
}

/*img{
  width:100%;
  height:100%;
  border:0px ;
}*/

</style>
<script src="menu/mootools.js" type="text/javascript"></script>

<script src="menu/3dcarousel.js" type="text/javascript"></script>

<style type="text/css">

```

```

/*Credits: By Santosh Setty (http://webdesigninfo.wordpress.com) */
/*Posted to: Dynamic Drive CSS Library (http://www.dynamicdrive.com/style/)
*/

.glossymenu{
    position: relative;
    padding: 0 0 0 10px;
    margin: 0 auto 0 auto;
    background: url(menu/menub_bg.gif) repeat-x; /*tab background image
path*/
    height: 46px;
    list-style: none;
}

.glossymenu li{
    float:left;
}

.glossymenu li a{
    float: left;
    display: block;
    color:#000;
    text-decoration: none;
    font-family: sans-serif;
    font-size: 15px;
    font-weight: bold;
    padding:0 0 0 18px; /*Padding to accomodate left tab image. Do not
change*/
    height: 46px;
    line-height: 46px;
    text-align: center;
    cursor: pointer;
}

.glossymenu li a b{
    float: left;
    display: block;
    padding: 0 20px 0 20px; /*Padding of menu items*/
}

.glossymenu li.current a, .glossymenu li a:hover{
    color: #fff;
    background: url(menu/menub_hover_left.gif) no-repeat; /*left tab image
path*/
    background-position: left;
}

.glossymenu li.current a b, .glossymenu li a:hover b{
    color: #fff;
    background: url(menu/menub_hover_right.gif) no-repeat right top;
/*right tab image path*/
}

</style>
<script type="text/javascript" language="JavaScript1.1">
<!--

```

```

/*
JavaScript Image slideshow:
By (www.wsabstract.com)
Over 200+ free JavaScript here!
*/

var slideimages=new Array()
var slidelinks=new Array()
function slideshowimages(){
for (i=0;i<slideshowimages.arguments.length;i++){
slideimages[i]=new Image()
slideimages[i].src=slideshowimages.arguments[i]
}
}

function slideshowlinks(){
for (i=0;i<slideshowlinks.arguments.length;i++)
slidelinks[i]=slideshowlinks.arguments[i]
}

function gotoshow(){
if (!window.winslide||winslide.closed)
winslide=window.open(slidelinks[whichlink])
else
winslide.location=slidelinks[whichlink]
winslide.focus()
}

//-->
</script>
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=iso-8859-1"
/>

<meta name="description" content="2011 International Conference on Computing
and Computer Vision" />

<meta content="Ziad Kobti" name="Author" />

<meta http-equiv="Content-Style-Type" content="text/css" />
<meta content="MSHTML 6.00.6000.16735" name="GENERATOR" />

<meta http-equiv="content-type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
<meta http-equiv="imagetoolbar" content="no" />
<meta name="keywords" content="slideman, slideman.js, javascript
slider, jquery, slideshow, effects" />
<meta name="description" content="Slideman.js - will do all the
sliding for you :)" />
<style type="text/css">
* { margin: 0; outline: none; }
body { background-color: #444444; }
.c { clear: both; }
#wrapper { margin: 0 auto; width: 560px; }
h2 { font-size: 24px; line-height: 40px; font-weight: normal;
color: #adc276; text-shadow: 0 1px 3px #222222; }
</style>

```

```
<style type="text/css">

/*Credits: Dynamic Drive CSS Library */
/*URL: http://www.dynamicdrive.com/style/ */

.sidebarmenu ul{
margin: 0;
padding: 0;
list-style-type: none;
font: bold 13px Verdana;
width: 170px; /* Main Menu Item widths */
border-bottom: 1px solid #ccc;
}

.sidebarmenu ul li{
position: relative;
}

/* Top level menu links style */
.sidebarmenu ul li a{
display: block;
overflow: auto; /*force hasLayout in IE7 */
color: white;
text-decoration: none;
padding: 6px;
border-bottom: 1px solid #778;
border-right: 1px solid #778;
}

.sidebarmenu ul li a:link, .sidebarmenu ul li a:visited, .sidebarmenu ul li
a:active{
background-color:#071D7D; /*background of tabs (default state)*/
}

.sidebarmenu ul li a:visited{
color: white;
}

.sidebarmenu ul li a:hover{
background-color: black;
}

/*Sub level menu items */
.sidebarmenu ul li ul{
position: absolute;
width: 170px; /*Sub Menu Items width */
top: 0;
visibility: hidden;
}

.sidebarmenu a.subfolderstyle{
background: url(right.gif) no-repeat 97% 50%;
}

/* Holly Hack for IE */
* html .sidebarmenu ul li { float: left; height: 1%; }
```

```
* html .sidebarmenu ul li a { height: 1%; }
/* End */
<style type="text/css">

/*Credits: Dynamic Drive CSS Library */
/*URL: http://www.dynamicdrive.com/style/ */

#ddblueblockmenu{
border: 1px solid black;
border-bottom-width: 0;
width: 185px;
}

#ddblueblockmenu ul{
margin: 0;
padding: 0;
list-style-type: none;
font: normal 90% 'Trebuchet MS', 'Lucida Grande', Arial, sans-serif;
}

#ddblueblockmenu li a{
display: block;
padding: 3px 0;
padding-left: 0px;
width: 169px; /*185px minus all left/right paddings and margins*/
text-decoration: none;
color: white;
background-color: #2175bc;
border-bottom: 1px solid #90bade;
border-left: 7px solid #1958b7;
}

* html #ddblueblockmenu li a{ /*IE only */
width: 187px; /*IE 5*/
width: 169px; /*185px minus all left/right paddings and margins*/
}

#ddblueblockmenu li a:hover {
background-color: #2586d7;
border-left-color: #1c64d1;
}

#ddblueblockmenu div.menutitle{
color: white;
border-bottom: 1px solid black;
padding: 1px 0;
padding-left: 0px;
background-color: black;
font: bold 90% 'Trebuchet MS', 'Lucida Grande', Arial, sans-serif;
}

</style>

<script type="text/javascript">
```

```

//Nested Side Bar Menu (Mar 20th, 09)
//By Dynamic Drive: http://www.dynamicdrive.com/style/

var menuids=["sidebarmenu1"] //Enter id(s) of each Side Bar Menu's main UL,
separated by commas

function initsidebarmenu(){
for (var i=0; i<menuids.length; i++){
    var ultags=document.getElementById(menuids[i]).getElementsByTagName("ul")
    for (var t=0; t<ultags.length; t++){
        ultags[t].parentNode.getElementsByTagName("a")[0].className+="
subfolderstyle"
        if (ultags[t].parentNode.parentNode.id==menuids[i]) //if this is a first
level submenu
            ultags[t].style.left=ultags[t].parentNode.offsetWidth+"px" //dynamically
position first level submenus to be width of main menu item
        else //else if this is a sub level submenu (ul)
            ultags[t].style.left=ultags[t-
1].getElementsByTagName("a")[0].offsetWidth+"px" //position menu to the right
of menu item that activated it
            ultags[t].parentNode.onmouseover=function(){
                this.getElementsByTagName("ul")[0].style.display="block"
            }
            ultags[t].parentNode.onmouseout=function(){
                this.getElementsByTagName("ul")[0].style.display="none"
            }
        }
        for (var t=ultags.length-1; t>-1; t--){ //loop through all sub menus again,
and use "display:none" to hide menus (to prevent possible page scrollbars
            ultags[t].style.visibility="visible"
            ultags[t].style.display="none"
        }
    }
}

if (window.addEventListener)
window.addEventListener("load", initsidebarmenu, false)
else if (window.attachEvent)
window.attachEvent("onload", initsidebarmenu)

</script>

<!-- sliderman.js -->
<script type="text/javascript" src="img/sliderman.1.2.1.js"></script>
<link rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" href="img/sliderman.css" />
<!-- /sliderman.js -->

<style type="text/css">.A {

    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; FONT-SIZE: 11px; FONT-FAMILY: Verdana,Arial; TEXT-
ALIGN: left; TEXT-DECORATION: none

}

```

```
.A:link {
    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #808080; TEXT-DECORATION: none
}

.A:visited {
    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #808080; TEXT-DECORATION: none
}

.A:hover {
    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #000080
}

.A:active {
    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #000080
}

.B {
    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; FONT-SIZE: 11px; FONT-FAMILY: Verdana,Arial; TEXT-
ALIGN: left; TEXT-DECORATION: none
}

.B:link {
    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #ffffcc; TEXT-DECORATION: none
}

.B:visited {
    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #ffffcc; TEXT-DECORATION: none
}

.B:hover {
    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: Black
}

.B:active {
    FONT-WEIGHT: bold; COLOR: #000080
}

.style1
```

```

    {
      width: 602px;
    }

    .style2
    {
      width: 171px;
    }
    .style3
    {
      width: 134px;
    }
  </style>

  <!--
  text-align:center
  font-style:oblique
  font-size:16;
  word-spacing:3em;letter-spacing:1em;text-transform:uppercase;vertical-
  align:super;line-height:120%
  -->

</head>
<body style="background-color:White" onload="Carousel()" >
  <form id="form1" runat="server">

    <div>
    <table border="0" cellpadding="0" width="100%" cellspacing="0">
      <tr>

        <td style="background-color:#071D7D;
        color:White; size:50%">

        <h1/><center /><strong />Time Series
        Forecast

        </td>

        <td style="background-color:#071D7D;
        size:5%">

        <!---->

```

```

align="top">





```

```

</ul></div></td>
  </tr>
  <tr valign="top">
    <td valign="top"><table cellpadding="0" style="vertical-align:top" cellspacing="5" border="0" ><tr valign="top">
      <td valign="top" width="12%">

        <table border="2" style="border-color:Blue">
          <tr style="height:6px">
            <td width="100%" style="background-color:#071D7D;color:White;height:4px;font-weight:bold">Forecasting <br />Legends</td>

          </tr>
          <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:20px">
            <td valign="top" align="center" style="padding-top:10px">
              
            </td>
          </tr>
          <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
            <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Reliable stocks,India</td>
          </tr>
          <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:10px">
            <td valign="top" align="center" style="padding-top:10px">
              
            </td>
          </tr>
          <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
            <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Xanther stocks,USA</td>
          </tr>
          <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:20px">
            <td valign="top" align="center" style="padding-top:10px">
              
            </td>
          </tr>
          <tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
            <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Monger stocks talks, UK</td>
          </tr>
        </table>
      </td>
      <td valign="top" class="style1">
        <table align="left" border="2" style="border-color:Blue" height="500px" width="100%">
          <tr style="height:5px">
            <td width="100%" valign="top" style="background-color:#071D7D;color:White;height:5px;font-weight:bold">Forecast</td>
          </tr>
        </table>
      </td>
    </tr>
  </tr>
</table>

```

```

        </tr>
        <tr style="height:580px">
            <td valign="top" align="left" style="font-
size:large; padding-left:10px;padding-right:10px;color:Black">
                <br /><FONT style="FONT-FAMILY: Verdana;
COLOR: #993300; FONT-SIZE: 16px;font-weight:bold"> </font><BR><br />

<table border="0" cellspacing="3" cellpadding="3" align="center" width="100%"
style="vertical-align:right ">
<tr align="left">
<center></center>
<td class="style2" align="center" >

<asp:DataGrid runat="server" ID="dgWeight">
<HeaderStyle BackColor="DarkOliveGreen" Font-Bold="true" ForeColor="White" />
<ItemStyle Font-Size="15px" />
<AlternatingItemStyle BackColor="AliceBlue" />
</asp:DataGrid></td>

    </tr>
    </table>
</td>
    </table>

        </div>

    </td>

</tr>
</table>

            </td>
            </tr>
            </table>
        </td>

        <!--<td valign="top" width="20%">
            <table align="left" border="2" style="border-color:Blue"
height="300px" width="100%">
                <tr><td valign="top" width="25%">
                    <table border="0" cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0">

                        <tr style="height:6px">
                            <td width="100%" style="background-
color:#071D7D;color:White;height:4px;font-weight:bold">Forecasting            <br
/>Legends</td>

                        </tr>
                    <tr style="height:70px;padding-top:20px">

```

```

        <td valign="top" align="center"
style="padding-top:10px">
        
</tr>
<tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
        <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-
Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Reliable stocks,India</td>
</tr>
<tr style="height:70px;padding-top:10px">
        <td valign="top" align="center"
style="padding-top:10px">
        
</tr>
<tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
        <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-
Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Xanther stocks,USA</td>
</tr>
<tr style="height:70px;padding-top:20px">
        <td valign="top" align="center"
style="padding-top:10px">
        
</tr>
<tr style="height:30px;padding-top:0px">
        <td align="center" style="font-family:Sans-
Serif;font-size:xx-small; font-style:italic">Monger stocks talks, UK</td>
</tr>
</table>
</td></tr></table>
</tr></table></td>

</tr>
</table>
</td>
</tr>
</table></div>
<!--<table align="left" border="1">
<tr align="left">
<td align="left">
<script type="text/javascript">

/*****
* Carousel Slideshow script- © Ger Versluis 2003
* Permission granted to DynamicDrive.com to feature script
* This notice must stay intact for legal use
* Visit http://www.dynamicdrive.com/ for full source code

```

```

*****/

/*****
Create a div with transparent place holder in your html
<div id="Carousel" style="position:relative">
    
</div>
placeholder width:
    4 sided: 1.42 * carousel image width + 3
    6 sided: 2 * carousel image width +4
    8 sided: 2.62 * carousel image width + 5
    12 sided: 3.87 * carousel image width + 7
placeholder height:
    carousel image height+2

Insert onload in body tag
    <body onload="Carousel()">
*****/

// 7 variables to control behavior
var Car_Image_Width=402;
var Car_Image_Height=202;
var Car_Border=true;           // true or false
var Car_Border_Color="white";
var Car_Speed=4;
var Car_Direction=true;       // true or false
var Car_NoOfSides=8;         // must be 4, 6, 8 or 12

/* array to specify images and optional links.
For 4 sided carousel specify at least 2 images
For 6 sided carousel specify at least 3
For 8 sided carousel specify at least 4
For 12 sided carousel specify at least 6
If Link is not needed keep it ""
*/
Car_Image_Sources=new Array(
    "images/a.jpg","",
    "images/b.jpg","",
    "images/c.jpg","", //this slide isn't linked
    "images/d.jpg","", // NOTE No comma after last line
);

/***** DO NOT EDIT BELOW *****/
CW_I=new Array(Car_NoOfSides/2+1);C_ClcW=new Array(Car_NoOfSides/2);
C_Coef=new Array(

    3*Math.PI/2,0,3*Math.PI/2,11*Math.PI/6,Math.PI/6,3*Math.PI/2,7*Math.PI/
4,    0,

    Math.PI/4,3*Math.PI/2,5*Math.PI/3,11*Math.PI/6,0,Math.PI/6,Math.PI/3);
var
C_CoefOf=Car_NoOfSides==4?0:Car_NoOfSides==6?2:Car_NoOfSides==8?5:9;
C_Pre_Img=new Array(Car_Image_Sources.length);
var
C_Angle=Car_Direction?Math.PI/(Car_NoOfSides/2):0,C_CrImg=Car_NoOfSides,C_Max
W,C_TotalW,

```

```

C_Stppd=false,i,C_LeftOffset,C_HalfNo=Car_NoOfSides/2;

function Carousel() {
    if (document.getElementById) {
        for (i=0; i<Car_Image_Sources.length; i+=2) {
            C_Pre_Img[i]=new
Image(); C_Pre_Img[i].src=Car_Image_Sources[i]}

    C_MaxW=Car_Image_Width/Math.sin(Math.PI/Car_NoOfSides)+C_HalfNo+1;
    Car_Div=document.getElementById("Carousel");
    for (i=0; i<C_HalfNo; i++) {

    CW_I[i]=document.createElement("img"); Car_Div.appendChild(CW_I[i]);
    CW_I[i].style.position="absolute";
    CW_I[i].style.top=0+"px";
    CW_I[i].style.height=Car_Image_Height+"px";
    if (Car_Border) {
        CW_I[i].style.borderStyle="solid";
        CW_I[i].style.borderWidth=1+"px";
        CW_I[i].style.borderColor=Car_Border_Color}
    CW_I[i].src=Car_Image_Sources[2*i];
    CW_I[i].lnk=Car_Image_Sources[2*i+1];
    CW_I[i].onclick=C_LdLnk;
    CW_I[i].onmouseover=C_Stp;
    CW_I[i].onmouseout=C_Rstrt}
    CarImages() }}

function CarImages() {
    if (!C_Stppd) {
        C_TotalW=0;
        for (i=0; i<C_HalfNo; i++) {

        C_ClcW[i]=Math.round(Math.cos(Math.abs(C_Coef[C_CoefOf+i]+C_Angle))*Car
_Image_Width);

        C_TotalW+=C_ClcW[i]}
    C_LeftOffset=(C_MaxW-C_TotalW)/2;
    for (i=0; i<C_HalfNo; i++) {
        CW_I[i].style.left=C_LeftOffset+"px";
        CW_I[i].style.width=C_ClcW[i]+"px";
        C_LeftOffset+=C_ClcW[i]}
    C_Angle+=Car_Speed/720*Math.PI*(Car_Direction?-1:1);

    if ((Car_Direction&&C_Angle<=0) || (!Car_Direction&&C_Angle>=Math.PI/C_Hal
fNo)) {
        if (C_CrImg==Car_Image_Sources.length) C_CrImg=0;
        if (Car_Direction) {
            CW_I[C_HalfNo]=CW_I[0];
            for (i=0; i<C_HalfNo; i++) CW_I[i]=CW_I[i+1];
            CW_I[C_HalfNo-
1].src=Car_Image_Sources[C_CrImg];
            CW_I[C_HalfNo-
1].lnk=Car_Image_Sources[C_CrImg+1]}
        else { for (i=C_HalfNo; i>0; i--) CW_I[i]=CW_I[i-1];
            CW_I[0]=CW_I[C_HalfNo];
            CW_I[0].src=Car_Image_Sources[C_CrImg];
            CW_I[0].lnk=Car_Image_Sources[C_CrImg+1]}
        C_Angle=Car_Direction?Math.PI/C_HalfNo:0; C_CrImg+=2}}

```

```

        setTimeout("CarImages()",50)

        function C_LdLnk(){if(this.lnk>window.location.href=this.lnk)
        function
C_Stp(){this.style.cursor=this.lnk?"pointer":"default";C_Stppd=true;}
        function C_Rstrt(){C_Stppd=false}
</script>
</td></tr></table>

        <table border="1"><tr><td><div id="Carousel" style="position:relative">

</div></td></tr></table>-->
        <%--<div>
        <div id="carousel">
        <div><a href="#"></a></div>

        <div><a href="#"></a></div>

        <div><a href="#"></a></div>

        <div><a href="#"></a></div>

        <div><a href="#"></a></div>

        <div><a href="#"></a></div>
</div>--%>
        </div>
        </form>
</body>
</html>

```

Server side:

```

using System;
using System.Collections;
using System.Configuration;
using System.Data;
using System.Linq;
using System.Web;
using System.Web.Security;
using System.Web.UI;
using System.Web.UI.HtmlControls;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls.WebParts;
using System.Xml.Linq;
using System.Data.SqlClient;

public partial class Forecast : System.Web.UI.Page
{

```

```

protected void Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    SqlConnection con = new
SqlConnection("Server=Personalpc;Database=suresh;Trusted_Connection=True");
    try
    {
        con.Open();
//        String Sqquery = "select  CompanyName as 'Company
Name',round(avg(cvalue),2) as 'ForecastValue' from cshare group by
companyname order by ForecastValue desc ";
        String Sqquery = "select distinct CompanyName as 'Company
Name',((cvalue*10)/100) as 'ForecastValue' from cshare order by ForecastValue
desc ";

        SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand(Sqquery, con);
        SqlDataAdapter Da = new SqlDataAdapter(Sqquery, con);
        DataSet ds = new DataSet();
        Da.Fill(ds);

//        gvDisplay.DataSource = ds;
//        gvDisplay.DataBind();

//        dtDisplay.DataSource = ds;
//        dtDisplay.DataBind();

        dgWeight.DataSource = ds;
        dgWeight.DataBind();
    }
    catch (Exception ex)
    {
        Response.Write(ex.Message);
    }
}
}

```